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A validation exercise to assess the ambition of city-level GHG emission reductions - Deliverable D1: Literature Review -

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Deliverable 1: Topical and literature reviews

This document provides a review of the literature on assessing the ambition of city-level GHG emission reductions. This includes a review on the methods for setting targets, deriving action plans and monitoring/reporting. It is the basis for developing a validation framework. It is used to implement the framework and confront validation results with literature findings. Part A is a topical compilation and Part B is a one-by-one review of literature and reference reports.

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Part A - Future review paper

Much of the world's population, up to 56%, lives in cities and urbanization is continuing to rapidly

increase ([World Bank 2020](#)). Currently, cities emit more GHG emissions than they store in their natural or managed pools ([AR6](#)). **In 2020, total urban emissions based on consumption-based accounting were estimated to be 28.5 ± 0.1 GtCO₂-eq, representing between 67-72% of global emissions ([AR6](#)).** Hence, cities are key to solving the global warming problem. It is imperative that cities reduce their GHG emissions and improve the uptake of carbon and other GHGs in pools ([AR6](#)).

Urban GHG emissions are principally caused by local or global transfer of carbon and other GHGs embodied in energy and raw materials (incl. food) used in the city. Understanding these transfers of GHG emissions between pools is a precursor to setting up measurable city-level emissions, reduction targets, and effective climate action plans.

In order to do so, cities need support therefore scientists and practitioners have developed different methods for this purpose. However, as the matter is complex and highly uncertain, these methods contain many methodological weaknesses and data problems. The goal of method developers is to reflect, as best as possible, the latest science and to align with the political ambition of the Paris Agreement (i.e. to limit global warming well below 2 degrees Celsius).

HVL was tasked by the Science-Based Target Network (SBTN) to undergo a validation exercise for three methodologies that cities use for setting decarbonization targets: [Deadline 2020](#) by the C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group (C40); [One Planet City Challenge](#) by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF); and [Tyndall Local Carbon Budget Tool](#) by Tyndall Center for Climate Change Research and University of Manchester.

The agreed purpose of the validation exercise was to scrutinize these selected methodologies with respect to their recommendations for setting science-based GHG emission reduction targets and related action plans. "Science-based" implies accounting for the latest research, which is why we carried out the following extensive literature research. The research provides the basis for developing a comprehensive [validation framework](#).

We started by reviewing the scientific community's latest compilation of research findings, which is provided by the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), in particular, Chapter 8: Urban Systems and Other Settlements. We continued by reviewing selected publications referenced therein. This initial review helps us to elicit topics that need to be covered in the validation exercise (third-party perspective). We follow up by discussions with SBTN (consortium benchmarking), additionally utilizing a verification questionnaire.

First Synthesis of Literature

A first synthesis with key findings of the literature is shown below. It was presented in a workshop.

- A **system perspective** is needed to understand the interlinkages between mitigation and adaptation. GHG emissions reduction targets need to be situated within a broader context. This includes the **analysis of co-benefits** of urban mitigation options and an evaluation of synergies and tradeoffs for **SDGs**. Taking a system perspective requires an integrated policy approach. However, note that Sethi et. al. 2020 assessing two intervention levels find that "The first is at the systems level ... interventions with smaller absolute scope demonstrate greater marginal mitigation potential than more system-wide interventions". For example,

public transport interventions are better than trying full-scale transport demand management.

- **City-level GHG accounting** is still under development and it is also not clear how to overcome the severe lack of base year data, in particular in developing countries and for non-CO2 emissions.
 - Best established are **methods** to account for urban production emissions. Less available are methods (and data) for accounting consumption-based emissions. A difficulty is, for example, to set an urban boundary and quantify transboundary urban GHG emissions as well as carbon footprints beyond urban and national administrative boundaries. This is also a matter of legislative power. Hence, an important topic of discussion is to what extent methods are covering all three scopes of emissions and GHGs; and whether they refer to carbon trading or other compensation schemes to account for weak and/or strong carbon leakage.
 - The **links between GHG transfers and resulting emissions** are also not yet sufficiently understood. For example, the link between emission profiles and city typologies (urban form, development, capacity, ...) is more complex as was found with new data. Improved frameworks/tools are becoming available, which are based on urban metabolism to account for interrelations and track energy and material flows. However, the demand for data by these new tools and technologies is immense which is why applications to cities are yet limited (and mostly only available to the Global North).
 - Another open methodological problem is systematic GHG accounting across scales, although progress was achieved (e.g. scaling-up of the different GHG accounting approaches).
- Methods for deriving **GHG reduction targets** are still under development (e.g. the problem of an insufficient understanding of the links between GHG transfers and resulting emissions).
 - New is the inclusion of historical and future urban GHG emissions for SSPs (1990-2100). However, uncertainties are high, especially because these scenarios had to be broken down to the city level.
 - Academic discussions around **fair burden sharing approaches** continue, but advances in equity concepts were achieved and are being taken up in the political arena. Equity implies accounting for equality, capability, and responsibility. However, uncertainties are high when choosing an approach to allocate national emission responsibilities to the city level. The choice of an allocation method strongly impacts the prospective target. Cost-effectiveness is a consideration that is entirely separate from that of equity. A globally cost-optimal implementation of mitigation efforts implies the possibility to trade mitigation outcomes.
- The scientific community and practitioners are continuously building experience in setting up, implementing, and assessing **city-level climate action plans**. Experience from different cities and a decade of action led to a number of important lessons learned to improve practical implementation and emission targets/action verification. These include:
 - Experiences stress the need for transparent and high quality monitoring, reporting, and communication. This is particularly important as the choice of methods (scaling down, allocation of responsibilities etc.) greatly impacts targets.

- Science stresses the need to think of mitigation together with adaptation. In particular, the role of green infrastructure in cities is emphasized.
- It is important to ensure multi-level governance and stakeholder engagement.
- Demand-side solutions are most often studied: "More than two-thirds of solutions are on the demand-side, and less than one-third on the supply side" (Sethi et al. 2020)

Review on Equity as a Measure of Mitigation Ambitions

Main Takeaways:

1. Equity implies accounting for equality, capability, and responsibility.
2. Equity based allocation approaches do not express where emissions need to be reduced, but rather what level of responsibility each actor has to achieve emission reductions.
3. Cost-effectiveness is a consideration that is entirely separate from that of equity.
4. Countries can achieve equitable ambitious trajectories while collectively ensuring a globally cost-optimal implementation.
5. A globally cost-optimal implementation of mitigation effort implies the possibility to trade mitigation outcomes

Equity as a Measure

Stopping global warming requires bringing GHG emissions to zero. Across nearly all countries, the Paris Agreement pursues limiting global warming to 1.5°C by reaching global net-zero emissions soon after mid-century. While **subnational actors (SNA)** are not parties to the international Paris Agreement, they are engaged in contributing and enabling the necessary mitigation measures. SNAs exist in various partnerships and initiatives.

The Paris Agreement does not specify the amount of emissions that each country, or SNA, should mitigate to reach its goal. Some SNAs have the resources and historical responsibility to reduce emissions faster than others and reach negative levels earlier to allow those in developing countries to prioritize other pressing development objectives.

The ambition of societies (i.e. groups of people as opposed to companies) in mitigating emissions is measured in light of **equity** considering their *circumstances*, their *needs for development*, their *capabilities* to achieve mitigations and *responsibilities* over past emissions. At the international level, the Paris Agreement requires all its objectives to be pursued equitably, reflecting countries' "Common but Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities" (**CBDR-RC**). Equity is the metric to assess the ambition of countries' mitigation pledges that are requested to justify how their NDCs are "fair and ambitious" ([FCCC, 2015](#)).

Subnational Potential for Climate Action

Only countries are signatories to the legally binding Paris Agreement. However, many other non-state actors and subnational constituents engage in global discussions on climate action and seek to contribute to limiting global warming.

Subnational actors can contribute to national mitigation targets and the ambition of their contribution should also be assessed through equity considerations that reflect their respective capabilities and responsibilities. In theory, the aggregation of the contributions of all countries' regions add up to the national total. In practice, unlike countries, SNAs (e.g. cities) can strongly rely on industry and agriculture whose emissions may not fall under the cities' responsibility. In some cases, this bias may favor cities transferring part of their emissions responsibility. Conversely, SNAs do not have full control over the emissions occurring in their territory and have more limited means to reduce emissions, which hinders their ability to implement mitigation measures. National governments often have control over many regulations and measures that can reduce SNAs' emissions. Additionally, part of a developed country's mitigation contribution can be provided through international finance of overseas mitigation, or conversely, part of a developing country's domestic mitigation can be conditional on receiving finance.

What is a “fair and ambitious” emissions target?

An equity or fairness-based metric measures the ambition of the whole mitigation outcome implied by a national or subnational target. The understanding of fairness defines the metric on which the ambition of an emissions target is assessed. Scientific studies have quantified equitable distribution of the remaining emissions space consistent with various levels of global warming ([IPCC AR6](#)). Note that the equity-based distributions can be applied to an emissions budget to allow for flexibility in the timing of mitigation measures, or directly to a dynamic emissions scenario ensuring consistency with global trajectories and allowing for progress tracking over time (see Box 1).

Box 1 - Emission Scenarios vs Carbon Budgets explanation.

Emissions scenarios vs. carbon budgets

Carbon (CO₂) budgets are often associated with national and global climate objectives. Due to the long lifetime of CO₂ in the atmosphere, the temperature at the end of the century depends on the cumulative CO₂ emissions rather than on the timing of those CO₂ emissions. A linear relationship links the cumulative CO₂ emissions to the maximal temperature over the century since the CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere by natural sinks (land and ocean) balances almost exactly the global temperature inertia in response to CO₂ emissions.

Carbon budgets relate global cumulative emissions over the century to temperature goals. However, using carbon budgets does not provide information on the cost-optimal timing on the mitigation measures to achieve the CO₂ mitigation. Carbon budgets also leave out considerations on the other GHG. By contrast, the GHG emissions scenarios from Integrated Assessment Models that budgets are based on are associated with specific policies and technology deployment that minimise the emissions mitigation costs. Directly using multi-gas emissions scenarios to derive national allocations preserves the information on cities' mitigation measures not just for CO₂, but for all the main greenhouse-gases (as defined in the Kyoto-Protocol: methane, nitrous oxide...).

Reflecting the absence of an agreed understanding of the principles of “equity” and “common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities, in the light of different national circumstances,” there is no globally agreed approach to burden sharing. A large number of “emissions allocation” schemes (also referred to as “effort-sharing approaches”), grounded in different ethical considerations, have been suggested by policy analysts and researchers ([Klinsky & Dowlatabadi, 2009](#); [Rao, 2014](#)). The approaches reviewed here provide quantifications of one or a combination of the following equity principles:

1. equality,
2. capability, and
3. responsibility.

Equity-based allocation approaches do not express where emissions need to be reduced, but rather what level of responsibility each actor has to achieve emission reductions, based on different equity interpretations. The allocation schemes are based on the presumption that subnational actors may also fulfill their emission reduction responsibility by contributing to emission reductions both inside and outside their jurisdiction.

Domestic Action and International Support as part of an Equitable Contribution

At the international level and under the UN negotiations, emissions attributed to countries are based on their physical location to the country where they occur (*emissions from international maritime and aviation activities are not attributed to countries*) since sovereign countries can only directly act on their territories. The territorial transformations needed to reduce emissions and align with the global goals are modeled using global socio-economic scenarios (using IPCC geographical and sectoral decarbonization indicators). The global mitigation scenarios consistent with the 1.5°C global warming threshold (or indeed any temperature target) are derived from models which determine where in the world emissions reductions can be achieved most cost-effectively. In this context that **cost-effectiveness is a consideration that is entirely separate from that of equity**. In other words, the degree to which it is appropriate to achieve emissions reductions in a particular country according to considerations of cost-effectiveness, as determined by a global mitigation pathway, is independent of the question of what is that country's "fair share,"

Domestic and equitable scenarios inform the two distinct responsibilities of countries to implement and fund mitigation, **countries can achieve equitable ambitious trajectories while collectively ensuring a globally cost-optimal implementation**. In practice, a developed country can implement domestic measures to align domestic emissions with the top-down scenarios.

For developed countries, this responsibility includes making a fair contribution by taking domestic emission reduction action and providing support to developing countries to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions. As the IPCC details in its 5th assessment report (WGIII, Box 3.2) "Financial flows between countries make it possible to separate the question of where mitigation should take place from the question of who should pay for it." This means that a developed country's fair share action scenario (red line in Figure 1) should be met by accounting for the sum of its domestic emission reductions (blue line in Figure 1) and emissions reductions it supports outside its boundaries (gray patch and green line on Figure 1). Conversely, a developing country could choose to sell part of its equitable emissions space to fund part of its transition along a more stringent domestic trajectory. It is important to note that pursuing an equitable trajectory only through international mechanisms for a developed country would not achieve the required domestic transition and be ultimately costlier. This international cooperation can now be facilitated with the adoption of a global market of mitigation outcomes (often called carbon market) under article 6 of the Paris Agreement.

Figure 1 | Schematic figure for a developed country where the equitable scenario (red) is more stringent than the domestic one (blue). To achieve the equitable scenario at least-cost, that country can buy the corresponding emissions space (green) by funding overseas mitigation (black) at a market price (yellow).

Figure 3 | Schematic figure for a developing country where the equitable scenario (red) is less stringent than the domestic one (blue). To fund the stringent domestic scenario at least-cost, that country can buy the corresponding emissions space (green) by funding overseas mitigation (black) at a market price (yellow).

Interpreting the results

How to understand cities' 1.5°C emissions ranges?

The results of the studies reviewed include the alignment emissions reduction levels for subnational actors (mostly cities) provided the following, potentially limited, considerations that SNAs have to implement this ambitious objective.

In practice, key considerations influence the cost and feasibility of attaining these emissions targets given SNAs' diverse circumstances. Firstly, SNAs may share or yield the decision power over key mitigation measures with the regional or national governments. SNAs' ability to implement these domestic mitigation measures may depend on external actors. Likewise, SNAs' capacity to mitigate emissions indirectly depends on their financial capacity which depends on national governance arrangements. Cities may need financial and policy support from national governments in order to achieve the targets derived here. Secondly, **a globally cost-optimal implementation of mitigation effort implies the possibility to trade mitigation outcomes**. In the absence of a global carbon market, one may consider inter-city agreements or face disproportionate cost to achieve their fair targets derived here through domestic mitigation only.

Part B - Literature reviews

AR6

Title: Climate Change 2022 - Mitigation of Climate Change - Working Group III Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: Urban Systems and Other Settlements

Author(s): IPCC Lead Authors - Xuemei Bai, Hilda Blanco, Kevin R. Gurney, Şiir Kılış, Oswaldo Lucon, Jin Murakami, Jiahua Pan, Ayyoob Sharifi, Yoshiki Yamagata

Description: The Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change focusing particularly on [Chapter 8 Urban Systems and other Settlements](#).

What is new since AR5:

- **AR5:** First standalone chapter on urban GHG (motivation: big emitters, catalysts of change, urbanization); [SR1.5](#) added that cities are places for managing demand for natural resources; cities are also featured as a key element in the transformational governance to tackle both climate change and biodiversity and ecosystem challenges in the first-ever [IPCC-IPBES co-sponsored workshop report](#); SDG 11; NUA - call for greening cities and the role for greening to achieve zero emission targets); **urban form** shapes urban energy consumption and GHG emissions;
- **AR6:** Includes more literature, more on the system's perspective to understand the **interlinkages between mitigation and adaptation**; situating GHG emissions reduction **targets within a broader context** (Bai et al. 2018; [Ürge-Vorsatz et al. 2018](#); Lin et al. 2021 - on adaptation and integrated solutions in general, less relevant here); more on **quantification of transboundary urban GHG emissions** and carbon footprint beyond urban and national administrative boundaries ([Chen et al. 2016](#); [Hu et al. 2016](#)).
- Inclusion of historical and future urban GHG emissions for SSPs (1990-2100)
- Analysis of **co-benefits** of urban mitigation options, including an evaluation of linkages with the SDGs based on synergies and/or trade-offs indicating the enablers and barriers of implementation
- **Looking forward to AR7:** New research priorities discussed in [Bai et al. 2018](#)

- **Urban GHG accounting:** Two main urban carbon accounting advances have occurred since AR5
 - **Better frameworks/tools based on urban metabolism to account for interrelations and track energy and material flows**, reflect differing perspectives on emissions responsibility and quantification effort. Synthesis point to four general frameworks: (1) territorial accounting (TA): focuses on in-city direct emission of GHGs to the atmosphere within a chosen geographic area; (2) community wide infrastructure supply chain footprinting (CIF): connects essential infrastructure use and demand activities in cities with their production, by combining TA emissions with the transboundary supply chain emissions associated with imported electricity, fuels, food, water, building materials, and waste management services used in cities; and (3 and 4) consumption-based carbon footprint accounting (CBCF) for personal carbon footprints (PCF) (which can be summed up for an area) and areal carbon footprint (ACF). CBCF: considers not only supply-chain-related GHG emissions of key infrastructure, but also emissions associated with all goods and services across a city, often removing emissions associated with goods and services exported from a city
 - **Series of methodological innovations facilitating practical implementation**, emissions verification, and scaling-up of the different GHG accounting approaches). Advances in six key areas: (1) advancing urban metabolism accounts integrating stocks and flows, and considering biogenic and fossil-fuel-based emissions (Chen et al. 2020b); (2) improving fine-scale and near-real-time urban use-activity data through new urban data science (Gately et al. 2017; Gurney et al. 2019; Turner et al. 2020; Yadav et al. 2021); (3) using atmospheric monitoring from the ground, aircraft, and satellites combined with inverse modeling to independently quantify TA emissions (Lamb et al. 2016; Lauvaux et al. 2016, 2020; Davis et al. 2017; Mitchell et al. 2018; Sargent et al. 2018; Turnbull et al. 2019; Wu et al. 2020a); (4) improving supply chain and input-output modeling, including the use of physically based input-output models (Wachs and Singh 2018); (5) establishing the global multi-region input-output models (Lenzen et al. 2017; Wiedmann et al. 2021); and (6) generating multi-sector use and supply activity data across all cities in a nation, in a manner where data aggregate consistently across city, province, and national scales (Tong et al. 2021) (see Section 8.3).
- **Adaptation** (see WG 2, chapter 6 on Cities, Settlements, and Key Infrastructure): Key risks (heat waves, flooding, starvation); adaptation of social infrastructure, nature-based solutions, and gray-physical infrastructure; case studies for Semarang (IDN), San Juan (Puerto Rico), Cities in SSA, cross working group box

General facts and relevance for justice dimension: The **urban share of global GHG emissions** (including CO₂ and CH₄) is substantive and continues to increase (high confidence). Total urban emissions based on consumption-based accounting were estimated to be 24.5 GtCO₂-eq, or 62% of the global total in 2015, excluding aviation, shipping and biogenics, and increased to an estimated 28.5 ± 0.1 GtCO₂-eq in 2020, representing about **67-72%** of global emissions. About 100 of the highest emitting urban areas account for approximately 18% of the global carbon footprint. {8.1.6, 8.3.3}. ... Urban land areas could triple between 2015 and 2050, with significant implications for

future carbon lock-in. The construction of new, and upgrading of, existing urban infrastructure through 2030 will result in significant emissions (very high confidence).

General facts on city's actions: There are growing local policy commitments, growing announcements of city ambitions, and more networking among them.

Relevant to judge ambition and action planning (indirectly target setting):

- Cities can only achieve net zero or near net zero GHG emissions through deep decarbonisation and systemic transformation (very high confidence). Urban deep decarbonisation entails implementing three broad strategies concurrently:
 - **Reducing urban energy consumption across all sectors**, including through compact and efficient urban forms and supporting infrastructure;
 - **Electrification and switching to net zero emissions resources**; and
 - **Enhancing carbon uptake and stocks** (medium evidence, high agreement). Given the regional and global reach of urban supply chains, a city cannot achieve net zero GHG emissions by only focusing on reducing emissions within its administrative boundaries. {8.1.6, 8.3.4, 8.4, 8.6}
- Include also scope 3 emissions

Relevant for testing the classification of cities: The urban share of regional GHG emissions increased between 2000 and 2015, with **much inter-region variation** in the magnitude of the increase (high confidence)... For 2000 to 2015, the urban emissions share across WGIII AR6 regions increased from 28% to 38% in Africa, from 46% to 54% in Asia and Developing Pacific, from 62% to 72% in Developed Countries, from 57% to 62% in Eastern Europe and West-Central Asia, from 55% to 66% in Latin America and Caribbean, and from 68% to 69% in the Middle East. {8.1.6, 8.3.3}. ...The potentials and sequencing of mitigation strategies to reduce GHG emissions will vary depending on a **city's land use and spatial form** and its **state of urbanization**, whether it is an established city with existing **infrastructure**, a rapidly growing city with new infrastructure, or an emerging city with infrastructure build-up (medium confidence). The long lifespan of urban infrastructures **locks in** behavior and committed emissions. Urban infrastructures and urban form can enable socio-cultural and lifestyle changes that can significantly reduce carbon footprints. **Growth typologies:** Rapidly growing cities can avoid higher future emissions through urban planning to co-locate jobs and housing to achieve compact urban form, and by leapfrogging to low-carbon technologies. Established cities will achieve the largest GHG emissions savings by replacing, repurposing, or retrofitting the building stock, strategic infilling and densifying, as well as through modal shift and the electrification of the urban energy system. New and emerging cities have unparalleled potential to become low or net zero GHG emissions while achieving high quality of life by creating compact, co-located, and walkable urban areas with mixed land use and transit-oriented design, that also preserve existing green and blue assets {8.2, 8.4, 8.6}. ... Most future urban population growth will occur in developing countries, where per capita 9 emissions are currently low but expected to increase with the construction and use of new 10 infrastructure and the built environment, and changes in incomes and lifestyles (very high 11 confidence). Distinguishing between 'consumer' and 'producer-city' (Chavez and Ramaswami 2013; Sudmant et al. 2018).

Relevant for recommendations on action plans:

- Given the dual challenges of rising urban GHG emissions and future projections of more frequent extreme climate events, there is an urgent **need to integrate urban mitigation and adaptation** strategies for cities to address climate change and withstand its effects (very high confidence).
- **Packages of mitigation policies** that implement **multiple urban-scale interventions** can have cascading effects across sectors, reduce GHG emissions outside of a city's administrative boundaries, and reduce more emissions than the net sum of individual interventions, particularly if **multiple scales of governance** are included (high confidence). Cities have the ability to implement policy packages across sectors using an urban systems approach, especially those that affect **key infrastructure** based on spatial planning, electrification of the urban energy system, and urban green and blue infrastructure. The **institutional capacity** of cities to develop, coordinate, and integrate sectoral mitigation strategies within their jurisdiction varies by context, particularly those related to governance, the regulatory system, and budgetary control. {8.4, 8.5, 8.6}. The IPCC separates into 7 main mitigation options: 1) Avoiding carbon-lock in, 2) Spatial planning, urban form and infrastructure, 3) Electrification and switching to net-zero emissions resources, 4) urban green and blue infrastructure, 5) Socio-behavioral aspects, 6) Urban-rural linkages, 7) Cross-sectoral integration
- Urban green and blue infrastructure can mitigate climate change through **carbon sequestration, avoided emissions, and reduced energy use** while offering multiple co-benefits (robust evidence, high agreement).
- **Opportunities to harness and enable informal practices and institutions in cities** related to housing, waste, energy, water, and sanitation to **reduce resource use** and mitigate climate change (low evidence, medium agreement).
- Achieving transformational changes in cities for climate change mitigation and adaptation will **require engaging multiple scales of governance**, including governments and non-state actors, and in connection with substantive financing beyond sectoral approaches (very high confidence).

Notes from the discussions on city-level GHG reduction strategies at the 12. [German-Japanese Energy Dialogue Forum](#):

- Active participation of citizens and the non-governmental sector is important
- Strategies should include recommendations to lower Scope 3 emissions
- It is more important to decarbonize middle dense cities and city-regions (Speckguertel, suburban/urban sprawl)
- Have a **system-dynamic and cross-sectoral perspective**, because sector-specific targets and action only are not sufficient in bringing down emissions (e.g., coordination between mobility and real estate sector as the value of land depends on infrastructure), focussing on the provision of the right infrastructure for change:
 - Infrastructure for low carbon transport/car-free cities
 - Education (e.g., educating engineers and consultancies on heat pumps; educating future cooks who are still learning heavy-meat based recipes)
 - Enabling digitized infrastructure (e.g., data and apps for pooled and shared mobility to increase number of people in cars)

- Three technologies are key and need to be scaled up: solar PV, heat pumps, and storage solutions

Ahn 2023

Title: CO2 emissions from C40 cities: citywide emission inventories and comparisons with global gridded emission datasets

Author(s): D Y Ahn, D L Goldberg, Toby Coombes, Gary Kleiman and S C Anenberg

Description: The paper compares city-reported CO2 emission data from the Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Emission Inventories (GPC) with gridded emission datasets from the Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) and the Open-Source Data Inventory for Anthropogenic CO2 (ODIAC) for 78 C40 cities.

Main findings:

- **ODIAC could be used to provide first-order estimates for citywide annual FFCO2 emissions**, especially for cities lacking reliable data-collecting systems. For 78 global cities' annual FFCO2 emissions, ODIAC agrees to GPC inventory within $\pm 62\%$ (1σ).
- **The level of agreement between ODIAC and GPC inventory varies by region:** African cities show the largest variability between ODIAC and GPC. ODIAC (1 km resolution) and EDGAR (0.1 resolution) tend to show better agreement toward GPC inventory for larger cities.
- **EDGAR is recommended for cities larger than 1,000 km².** For emission trend estimates, the study shows that **neither the current version of ODIAC2020b nor EDGARv60 are suitable for tracking citywide emission mitigation progress** at a policy-relevant scale.
- Sources of emissions discrepancies:
 - **Variation in spatial proxies used for disaggregating national emissions** (i.e., population settlements for EDGAR and nighttime light intensity for ODIAC)
 - **Point emission sources** (e.g. inconsistent accounting of power plants between GPC inventory and not keeping up with the up-to-date operation status)
 - **Emissions factors used in GPC inventories** - The Average years of emission factors documented in GPC inventories are 2007 for African cities, 2010 for Latin American cities, and 2016 for North American and European cities. The lack of local-specific and up-to-date emission factors data has been considered a major challenge in developing the GHG emissions inventory with African cities having to depend on international rather than local emission factors.
 - **Uncertainty in national FFCO2 Emission** (3.5% to 50% according to some sources)

Figure 4. Comparison of scope 1 fossil fuel CO₂ (FFCO₂) emissions for 78 C40 cities estimated from the GPC emission Inventories against the EDGAR (left panels) and ODIAC (right panels).

Anderson et al. 2020

Title: A factor of two: how the mitigation plans of ‘climate progressive’ nations fall far short of Paris-compliant pathways

Author(s): Kevin Anderson, John F. Broderick & Isak Stoddard

Description: This article criticizes current methods of dividing carbon budgets and targets.

Main Relevant Findings:

- The article derives Paris-compliant carbon budgets with a fair eye and excludes negative emission technologies, focusing on carbon emissions arising from energy, applied to the UK and Sweden.
- Includes a brief review of carbon budget developments from AR5, SR1.5 to AR6
- Takes a global carbon budget of 716 GtCO₂ from 2020 (all courses, Paris compliant) but subtracts "Global overhead" (i.e. a justice consideration which makes the connected emissions a global/sector responsibility and rather than a national one) which leaves a Paris-compliant carbon budget of **656 GtCO₂ from 2020 onwards**.
- Global overhead includes:
 - Cement emissions, which range between a factor 2-5 and are included because cement is key for development. The road map from IEA 2018 set the goal of a 60 GtCO₂ carbon budget starting from 2020 in the optimistic scenario with growth,

sector commitment should be 140 GtCO₂ (5.1% growth) and 100 GtCO₂ (3.4% growth) between 2020-2075.

- Deforestation which balances out to zero as it is assumed that between 2020 and 2100, emissions from deforestation and degradation are balanced by the carbon uptake in managed LULUCF sequestration.
- Has 4 different groupings of countries, depending on GDP, pop, emissions, and oil resources. For developing countries, the remaining budget ranges between 95-136 GtCO₂.
- Population-based allocations do not take into account historical emissions, capacity to finance decarbonization, renewable energy resources, the inertia of existing high-carbon and fossil-fuel infrastructure, nor the carbon intensity of the existing economy.
- The UK (SWE) emissions pathway implies a carbon budget at least **a factor of two** (2.5) greater than the UK's Paris-compliant budget estimated in the paper. Instead of 5% annual reduction rates, they should be 10 (12)%, respectively. Note that this is the result for rather climate-progressive nations. So, the realistic Paris-compliant reduction rates are hardly discussed.

Bai et al. 2018

Title: Six Research Priorities for Cities and Climate Change

Author(s): Xuemei Bai, Richard J. Dawson, Diana Ürge-Vorsatz, Gian C. Delgado, Aliyu Salisu Barau, Shobhakar Dhakal, David Dodman, Lykke Leonardsen, Valérie Masson-Delmotte, Debra C. Roberts & Seth Schultz

Description: A commentary elaborating on the "Urban development challenge" wherein the lack of long-term studies of urban climates and their impacts makes it hard for city officials to plan decades ahead

Main Relevant Findings:

- The paper inform about IPCC Cities and Climate Change Science Conference: <https://citiesipcc.org>
- Six priorities for cities and climate-change research
 - **Expand observations.** Researchers and city authorities need to extend the quantity and types of urban data collected; city- and nationwide data are not good enough. Reliable inventories of greenhouse gasses are needed — from individual dwellings, factories, and roads — as well as methods for verifying them
 - **Understand climate interactions.** Climate processes are complex — more so in cities. Examples: [Melbourne with bluestone pavements](#), the impact of reflective roads and roofs, [as tried in New York](#) and Los Angeles
 - **Study informal settlements.** By 2050, three billion people, mostly in the global south, will be living in slums.
 - **Harness disruptive technologies.** The digital revolution is transforming cities. For example, urban shared-mobility schemes have improved air quality and social inclusion, and [reduced congestion](#); Affordable materials and technologies
 - **Support transformation** through bold strategies and scaling up measures of good local innovation.

- **Recognize global sustainability context (aka carbon leakage).** Cities are open, complex, dynamic systems with a global reach. Well-intended local actions can displace issues to other sectors or into the future.
- Stronger partnerships, better financial support, and better platforms (one mentioned: [Future Earth's Urban Knowledge-Action Network](#)) are needed.
 - Note: Good to cite for motivation of our SBTN joined article: Scientists should become more engaged with policy and practice networks such as C40 Cities, ICLEI Local Governments for Sustainability and United Cities and Local Governments.

[Hsu et al. 2022](#)

Title: Predicting European cities' climate mitigation performance using machine learning

Author(s): Angel Hsu, Xuewei Wang, Jonas Tan, Wayne Toh & Nihit Goyal

Description: Results of developing a predictive machine learning model using self-reported carbon emissions data from 6,000 European cities in the EUCom.

Main Relevant Findings:

- The model was able to explain 90% of the variation between the cities' self-reported emissions data and predicted emission values.
- It determined that cities signed into the EUCom were more likely to have achieved their 2020 emissions reduction targets and were more likely to reduce emissions than cities that did not: 74% of EUCom cities likely reduced emissions from their baseline vs 53% of non-EUCom cities but the link is not causal.
- It showed that EUCom cities that set ambitious reduction targets, established a baseline, and measured and reported results had a greater emissions reduction than EUCom cities that did not. Prior research indicates that this is likely due to the fact that accomplishing these tasks indicate a city's means of implementation (e.g. financial support to implement emission reduction activities).

[Balouktsi et al. 2020](#)

Title: Carbon metrics for cities: production and consumption implications for policies

Author(s): Maria Balouktsi

Description: An interpretative synthesis of existing research to explore the differences between three emerging approaches to city-level GHG emissions accounting based on methodological dimensions: boundary-setting, categorization of emissions, and emissions type.

Main Relevant Findings:

- The analysis of actual 'net-zero emission' concepts used by eight cities revealed that their **precise meaning and applicability remain ambiguous.**
- The figure below is an overview of the dimensions needed for the clarification of net-zero emission and similar targets on the city level:

Carbon metric				Reduction targets			Proof of climate neutrality
Type of emissions	Scope of emissions	Emission sources (source-based approach)	Emission inducers (consumer-based approach)	Reference unit	Use of scenarios	Target year	Compensations and offsets
Only CO ₂ OR CO ₂ , CH ₄ and N ₂ O OR GHGs covered by the Kyoto Protocol OR GHGs covered by the IPCC	Scope 1: direct emissions from sources located within the city boundary AND/OR Scope 2: indirect emissions from the use of grid-supplied electricity, heat, steam and cooling within the city boundary AND/OR Scope 3: all other indirect emissions that occur outside of the city boundary due to in-boundary activities	Stationary energy AND/OR Transportation AND/OR Waste management AND/OR Industrial processes and product use AND/OR Agriculture and forestry	Households: a housing, mobility, nutrition, private consumption AND/OR Government: a public buildings, public infrastructure, public energy plants, public transport, public construction, other goods/services AND/OR Business capital: a buildings, infrastructure, transport, etc.	Tonnes of CO ₂ /CO ₂ e AND/OR tonnes of CO ₂ /CO ₂ e per capita AND/OR tonnes of CO ₂ /CO ₂ e per household AND/OR tonnes of CO ₂ /CO ₂ e per product output AND/OR Land use (hectares as part of an ecological footprint) per capita	No scenario modelling OR External factors: a migration (inter-)national economic developments, national policies, energy price development, technological advancements, consumer behaviour, etc. AND/OR Internal factors: a other planned large-scaled investments in the city, new organisations take lead, etc.	2050 OR 2040 OR 2035 OR 2030 OR 2025	Credits for green procurement AND/OR Counting of recycling benefits AND/OR Purchase of carbon credits AND/OR Sale of excess energy production AND/OR Natural carbon sinks (e.g. forests/parks) AND/OR Carbon capture and storage OR No compensation or offset

- Although cities should be allowed a certain level of freedom to account for emissions in ways that increase the relevance for local policy-making, an essential requirement will be for cities to systematically report their estimates and targets following a standardized typology of system boundaries and other dimensions. **Transparency is key.**

[Chen et al. 2016](#)

Title: Transnational city carbon footprint networks – Exploring carbon links between Australian and Chinese cities

Author(s): Guangwu Chen, Thomas Wiedmann, Yafei Wang, Michalis Hadjikakou

Description: Results of constructing a multi-scale, global MRIO model to describe a transnational city carbon footprint network among five Chinese megacities and the five largest Australian capital cities in an attempt to focus on inter-city and inter-country carbon flows between two trading partners.

- City input-output tables are nested in the final MRIO
- The city carbon footprint defined in the study is designed to avoid double counting by deducting emissions embodied in exports from total emissions. In brief, the **city carbon footprint (CF)** equals the sum of all 8 territorial GHG emissions, plus emissions embodied in imports (**EEI**), minus emissions embodied in exports (**EEE**). The remaining territorial emissions (**RTE**) are defined as territorial emissions minus EEE. **The CF thus accounts for all emissions associated with the final demand for products in the city.**

Main Relevant Findings:

- The figure below is an analysis of city carbon footprints by sector

- The largest percentage of CF of Chinese municipalities comes from the construction sectors (up to 40%)
- For Australian cities, the construction, transport, and food and beverage sectors makeup about 40% of CF while the rest is allocated to goods and services
- The study of carbon footprint networks reveals a disparity of regional CFs, RTE, and EEI. Chinese cities have lower RTE because of limited land, resources, and large populations while Australian cities share higher RTE due to lower population densities. The EEI from the rest of China, the rest of Australia, and the rest of the world to Australian cities make up about half of their CFs whereas the EEI from the rest of China to Chinese cities constitutes most of their CFs. This indicates the high-carbon intensity production system and high mitigation potentials in the rest of China.
- **Per-capita emissions are also not determined by the development status of Australia and China, but by the economic idiosyncrasies of the cities themselves.**

[Hachaichi et al. 2021](#)

Title: Virtual carbon emissions in the big cities of middle-income countries

Author(s): Mohamed Hachaichi and Tahar Baouni

Description: **Assessment of 252 cities** in middle-income countries using extended environmental Input-Output Analysis (IOA).

- City-level IO tables are not available which is why the national tables were used.
- Consumer expenditure surveys were also used.

Main Relevant Findings:

- City-level IO tables are not available which is why the national tables were used.

- Consumer expenditure surveys were also used.
- Carbon emissions in big cities of middle-income countries are 40% due to the food sector, followed by education and health (11%), electricity and water, and transport (both 10%).
- For UMICS, policymakers should double focus on food and transport, while for LMICS they should triple focus (also on electricity, gas, & water)
- The study provides a first glimpse of **cross-city carbon footprint** comparison of middle-income class (upper, lower) with **focus on sectoral decomposition**; Moran et al. 2018: 14.88 +- 6.01 tCO₂ average for developed cities
- References Lee et al. 2021 carbon footprint which could be a golden stepping stone for developing countries (India as a case study)

Huo et al. 2022

Title: Carbon Monitor Cities near-real-time daily estimates of CO₂ emissions from 1500 cities worldwide

Author(s): Da Huo, Xiaoting Huang, Xinyu Dou, Philippe Ciais, Yun Li, Zhu Deng, Yilong Wang, Duo Cui, Fouzi Benkhelifa, Taochun Sun, Biqing Zhu, Geoffrey Roest, Kevin R. Gurney, Piyu Ke, Rui Guo, Chenxi Lu, Xiaojuan Lin, Arminel Lovell, Kyra Appleby, Philip L. DeCola, Steven J. Davis & Zhu Liu

Description: The authors present and analyze a new city-level dataset of fossil fuel and cement emissions, 'Carbon Monitor Cities', which provides daily estimates of emissions from January 2019 through December 2021 for a cohort of cities. The method builds on near-real-time (NRT) and spatially explicit estimates of daily carbon dioxide.

Main Relevant Findings:

- The goal of the Carbon Monitor Cities' dataset is to improve city-level emission inventories and includes estimates for both functional urban areas and city administrative areas that are consistent with global and regional totals.
- The paper describes and attempts to improve upon the challenges faced by currently used emission datasets (i.e. GPC and CDP-ICLEI) by addressing
 - **Coverage** (i.e. Inconsistent boundaries)
 - **Timeliness** (i.e. large lagtime in data acquisition)
 - **Temporal Resolution** (i.e. near-real-time rather than 2-5 year old emission data)
- The dataset in the paper presents daily estimates of emissions from January 2019 through December 2021 for 1500 cities in 46 countries, and disaggregates five sectors: power generation, residential (buildings), industry, ground transportation, and aviation.
- Comparisons with other datasets (i.e. CEADs, MEIC, Vulcan, and CDP-ICLEI Track) were performed, and the authors estimate the overall annual uncertainty range to be $\pm 21.7\%$
- The dataset (Carbon Monitor Cities) is downscaled from the Carbon Monitor, which is a NRT national level emission dataset at a global scale
- The paper demonstrates some of the shortcomings of the current emissions datasets and collection methods and highlights a method that is likely to become more prominent in emission account in the near future

Fankhauser et al. 2022

Title: The meaning of net zero and how to get it right

Author(s): Sam Fankhauser, Stephen M. Smith, Myles Allen, Kaya Axelsson, Thomas Hale, Cameron Hepburn, J. Michael Kendall, Radhika Khosla, Javier Lezaun, Eli Mitchell-Larson, Michael Obersteiner, Lavanya Rajamani, Rosalind Rickaby, Nathalie Seddon & Thom Wetzer

Description: The authors offer a series of interpretations of what net-zero means and how it should be achieved. They settle on seven attributes they find help ensure consistency with global temperature goals while embedding net-zero into socio-political and legal contexts.

Main Relevant Findings:

- It makes little sense to apply the net-zero concept on timescales shorter than decades. Achieving net zero through an unsustainable combination of fossil-fuel emissions and short-term removals is ultimately pointless. Thus, carbon emissions and removals must balance over multi-decadal timescales
- SBTN uses the term net-zero simply to describe emissions trajectories consistent with 1.5 °C. While a helpful shorthand, this obscures the fact that halting global warming, at whatever temperature level, requires net-zero CO₂ emissions and declining non-CO₂ radiative forcing.
- The authors set out the criteria in the figure to the right as ‘guardrails’ to ensure the robustness of net zero as a framework for climate action.
 1. Front-loaded Emission Reductions
 - Every year of delay before initiating emission reductions decreases the remaining time to reach net-zero while keeping below 1.5 °C by approximately two years
 - Early action reduces the threat of carbon cycle feedbacks
 - Economic models also show it to be the most cost-effective way to reach a temperature target
 - A long-term target with interim targets is advised for governments with some level of robust enforcement (e.g. legislation or enforceable regulations)

Fig.2

Attributes of net zero as a frame of reference.

2. Comprehensive Emissions Reduction: Net-zero means all emission scopes and sources need to be covered and all stakeholders need to be involved
3. Cautious use of Carbon Dioxide Removal: Removal will probably be constrained by cost considerations and geopolitical factors, as well as by biological, geological, technological and institutional limitations on our ability to remove carbon from the atmosphere and store it durably and safely.
4. Effective Regulation of Carbon Offsets: Previous experience with carbon offset markets suggests that the environmental integrity of carbon offsets will be problematic, unless quality standards are upgraded and scrupulously enforced
5. An Equitable Transition to Net-zero: The Paris Agreement is explicit about the need for an equitable transition and implies some countries may need to reach net zero faster, every country may chart its own path to net zero tailored to its own specific national circumstances and constraints, and developing countries need to be supported—in terms of finance, technology and capacity building—in reaching net zero.
6. Socio-ecological Sustainability: Rather than narrowly pursuing one objective—carbon storage—net-zero plans must acknowledge a full range of ecosystem services and be embedded into broader strategies for socio-ecological sustainability
7. New Economic Opportunities: As attractive net-zero solutions begin to emerge, it will increasingly become clear that net zero can also be an economic opportunity. A just transition is possible, but it requires close collaboration between government, industry, labour unions and local communities, and substantial investment in education, skills and social protection.

[Fry et al. 2018](#)

Title: Assessing carbon footprints of cities under limited information

Author(s): Jacob Fry, Manfred Lenzen, Yutong Jin, Takako Wakiyama, Timothy Baynes, Thomas Wiedmann, Arunima Malik, Guangwu Chen, Yafei Wang, Arne Geschke, Heinz Schandl

Description: The paper explores potential errors and uncertainties associated with city carbon footprinting and identifies levels of data availability that do not allow calculation of sufficiently accurate carbon footprints.

Main Relevant Findings:

- Applied mainly to Chinese cities because they have Multi-regional Input-Output (MRIO) tables, interregional trade tables, and they compare against the Leontief production function approach.
- High sectoral aggregation can lead to unacceptable errors
- Missing import data make the use of an MRIO table for comparative city analysis unachievable
- A city's economic feedback onto itself is usually quite weak
- The lack of data and frameworks that embed city I-O tables in national and regional tables is an important obstacle for evidence-based policymaking. Only if multi-layered I-O frameworks (i.e. national frameworks that explicitly represent economic structure, final demand of cities,

and relationship to domestic and international trade) exist, a city's true supply chain is accounted for. **Environmental footprint calculations should therefore always come together with uncertainty estimates**

[Kanemoto et al. 2016](#)

Title: Mapping the Carbon Footprint of Nations | Environmental Science & Technology (acs.org)

Author(s): Keiichiro Kanemoto, Daniel Moran, and Edgar G. Hertwich

Description: The paper presents a new spatially explicit carbon footprint method for establishing a better link between downstream users to facilities and regulators. It also locates emission hotspots driven by a given set of consumers

Main Relevant Findings:

- For most developed countries the **carbon footprint has diluted and spread**. For example, since 1970 the U.S. carbon footprint has grown 23% territorially, and 38% in consumption-based terms, but nearly 200% in spatial extent (i.e., the minimum area needed to contain 90% of emissions).
- China and India don't show similar spatial expansion of consumption footprints. In their case, urbanization concentrates their domestic pollution and this offsets the increasing importance of imports.

[Kii 2021](#)

Title: Projecting future populations of urban agglomerations around the world and through the 21st century

Author(s): Masanobu Kii

Description: The paper estimates population trends using SSPs until 2100 for approx. 20,000 urban agglomerations in 151 countries. Data is given in steps of 10 years.

Main Relevant Findings:

- Urban growth in this century will produce increasingly concentrated cities, some growing to enormous sizes
- Although detailed urbanization trajectories differ for different SSP scenarios, in all cases, the largest projected agglomerations of the future are more populous than the current largest agglomerations

[Kikstra et al. 2022](#)

Title: The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report WGIII climate assessment of mitigation pathways: from emissions to global temperatures

Author(s): Oskar Krabbe, Giel Linthorst, Kornelis Blok, Wina Crijns-Graus, Detlef P. van Vuuren, Niklas Höhne, Pedro Faria, Nate Aden and Alberto Carrillo Pineda

Description: Summarizes methodological differences in emission scenarios and global carbon budgets from former reports to AR6. See in particular Section 2.1.2.

Main Relevant Findings:

- Revisions were made to historical temperature records
- climate sensitivities were updated, leading to higher near-term warming projections
- Overall, estimates are similar but most 1.5D cp pathways will overshoot.
- See also two related carbon briefs going into detail.
 - <https://www.carbonbrief.org/analysis-what-the-new-ipcc-report-says-about-when-world-may-pass-1-5c-and-2c/>
 - <https://www.carbonbrief.org/in-depth-qa-the-ipccs-sixth-assessment-report-on-climate-science/#onefive>

Table 2.4 | Emissions in 2030, 2050 and 2100 in 1.5°C and 2°C scenario classes and absolute annual rates of change between 2010–2030, 2020–2030 and 2030–2050, respectively.

Values show median and interquartile range across available scenarios (25th and 75th percentile given in brackets). If fewer than seven scenarios are available (*), the minimum–maximum range is given instead. Kyoto-GHG emissions are aggregated with GWP-100 values from IPCC AR4. Emissions in 2010 for total net CO₂, CO₂ from fossil-fuel use and industry, and AFOLU CO₂ are estimated at 38.5, 33.4, and 5 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹, respectively (Le Quéré et al., 2018). Percentage reduction numbers included in headline statement C.1 in the Summary for Policymakers are computed relative to 2010 emissions in each individual pathway, and hence differ slightly from a case where reductions are computed relative to the historical 2010 emissions reported above. A difference is reported in estimating the ‘anthropogenic’ sink by countries or the global carbon modelling community (Grassi et al., 2017), and AFOLU CO₂ estimates reported here are thus not necessarily comparable with countries’ estimates. Scenarios with year-2010 Kyoto-GHG emissions outside the range assessed by IPCC AR5 WGIII are excluded (IPCC, 2014b), as a scenario duplicates that would bias ranges towards a single study.

Name	Category	#	Annual emissions/sequestration (GtCO ₂ yr ⁻¹)			Absolute Annual Change (GtCO ₂ yr ⁻¹)			Timing of Global Zero Year
			2030	2050	2100	2010–2030	2020–2030	2030–2050	
Total CO ₂ (net)	Below-1.5°C	5*	13.4 (15.4, 11.4)	–3.0 (1.7, –10.6)	–8.0 (–2.6, –14.2)	–1.2 (–1.0, –1.3)	–2.5 (–1.8, –2.8)	–0.8 (–0.7, –1.2)	2044 (2037, 2054)
	1.5°C-low-OS	37	20.8 (22.2, 18.0)	–0.4 (2.7, –2.0)	–10.8 (–8.1, –14.3)	–0.8 (–0.7, –1.0)	–1.7 (–1.4, –2.3)	–1.0 (–0.8, –1.2)	2050 (2047, 2055)
	1.5°C with no or limited OS	42	20.3 (22.0, 15.9)	–0.5 (2.2, –2.8)	–10.2 (–7.6, –14.2)	–0.9 (–0.7, –1.1)	–1.8 (–1.5, –2.3)	–1.0 (–0.8, –1.2)	2050 (2046, 2055)
	1.5°C-high-OS	36	29.1 (36.4, 26.0)	1.0 (6.3, –1.2)	–13.8 (–11.1, –16.4)	–0.4 (0.0, –0.6)	–1.1 (–0.5, –1.5)	–1.3 (–1.1, –1.8)	2052 (2049, 2059)
	Lower-2°C	54	28.9 (33.7, 24.5)	9.9 (13.1, 6.5)	–5.1 (–2.6, –10.3)	–0.4 (–0.2, –0.6)	–1.1 (–0.8, –1.6)	–0.9 (–0.8, –1.2)	2070 (2063, 2079)
	Higher-2°C	54	33.5 (35.0, 31.0)	17.9 (19.1, 12.2)	–3.3 (0.6, –11.5)	–0.2 (–0.0, –0.4)	–0.7 (–0.5, –0.9)	–0.8 (–0.6, –1.0)	2085 (2070, post-2100)

Table TS.3 | GHG, CO₂ emissions and warming characteristics of different mitigation pathways submitted to the AR6 scenarios database, and as categorised in the climate assessment. (Table 3.2)

p50 [p5–p95] *			GHG emissions (GtCO ₂ -eq yr ⁻¹) *			GHG emissions reductions from 2019 (%) *			Emissions milestones ¹⁾				Cumulative CO ₂ emissions (GtCO ₂) *		Cumulative net-negative CO ₂ emissions (GtCO ₂)	Global mean temperature changes 50% probability (°C) *		Likelihood of peak global warming staying below (%) *		
Category ²⁾	Category/subset label	WGI SSP & WGIII (P ₂ /MPs alignment) ³⁾	2030	2040	2050	2030	2040	2050	Peak CO ₂ emissions (% peak before 2100)	Peak GHG emissions (% peak before 2100)	Net zero CO ₂ (% net zero pathways)	Net zero GHGs (% net zero pathways) ⁴⁾	2020 to net zero CO ₂	2020–2100	Year of net zero CO ₂ to 2100	at peak warming	2100	<1.5°C	<2.0°C	<3.0°C
<p>Modelled global emissions pathways categorised by projected global warming levels (GWL). Detailed likelihood definitions are provided in SPM Box 1. The five illustrative scenarios (SSP-x) considered by AR5 WGI and the illustrative (Mitigation) Pathways assessed in WGIII are aligned with the temperature categories and are indicated in a separate column. Global emission pathways contain regionally differentiated information. This assessment focuses on their global characteristics.</p> <p>Projected median annual GHG emissions in the year across the scenarios, with the 5th–95th percentile in brackets. Modelled GHG emissions in 2019: 55 [53–58] GtCO₂-eq.</p> <p>Projected median GHG emissions reductions of pathways in the year across the scenarios compared to modelled 2019, with the 5th–95th percentile in brackets. Negative numbers indicate increase in emissions compared to 2019.</p> <p>Median 5-year intervals at which projected CO₂ & GHG emissions peak, with the 5th–95th percentile interval in square brackets. Percentage of peaking pathways is denoted in round brackets. Three dots (...) denotes emissions peak in 2100 or beyond for that percentile.</p> <p>Median 5-year intervals at which projected CO₂ & GHG emissions reach net zero, with the 5th–95th percentile interval in square brackets. Percentage of net zero pathways is denoted in round brackets. Three dots (...) denotes net zero not reached for that percentile.</p> <p>Median cumulative net CO₂ emissions across the projected scenarios in this category until reaching net zero or until 2100, with the 5th–95th percentile interval in square brackets.</p> <p>Median cumulative net-negative CO₂ emissions between the year of net zero CO₂ and 2100. More net-negative results in greater temperature declines after peak.</p> <p>Projected temperature change of pathways in this category (50% probability across the range of climate uncertainties), relative to 1850–1900, at peak warming and in 2100, for the median value across the scenarios and the 5th–95th percentile interval in square brackets.</p> <p>Median likelihood that the projected pathways in this category stay below a given global warming level, with the 5th–95th percentile interval in square brackets.</p>																				
C1 [97]	limit warming to 1.5°C (>50%) with no or limited overshoot	SSP1-1.9, SP	31 [21–36]	17 [6–23]	9 [1–15]	43 [34–60]	69 [58–90]	84 [73–98]			2095–2100 (52%) [2050–...]		510 [330–710]	320 [–210 to 570]	–220 [–660 to –20]	1.6 [1.4–1.6]	1.3 [1.1–1.5]	38 [33–58]	90 [86–97]	100 [99–100]
C1a [50]	... with net zero GHGs	LD	33 [22–37]	18 [6–24]	8 [0–15]	41 [31–59]	66 [58–89]	85 [72–100]	2020–2025 (100%) [2020–2025]		2070–2075 (100%) [2050–2090]		550 [340–760]	160 [–220 to 620]	–360 [–680 to –140]	1.6 [1.4–1.6]	1.2 [1.1–1.4]	38 [34–60]	90 [85–98]	100 [99–100]
C1b [47]	... without net zero GHGs	Ren	29 [21–36]	16 [7–21]	9 [4–13]	48 [35–61]	70 [62–87]	84 [76–93]			... [0%] [...]		460 [320–590]	360 [10–540]	–60 [–440 to 0]	1.6 [1.5–1.6]	1.4 [1.3–1.5]	37 [33–56]	89 [87–96]	100 [99–100]
C2 [133]	return warming to 1.5°C (>50%) after a high overshoot	Neg	42 [31–55]	25 [17–34]	14 [5–21]	23 [0–44]	55 [40–71]	75 [62–91]	2020–2025 (100%) [2020–2025]		2055–2060 (100%) [2045–2070]	2070–2075 (87%) [2055–...]	720 [530–930]	400 [–90 to 620]	–360 [–680 to –60]	1.7 [1.5–1.8]	1.4 [1.2–1.5]	24 [15–42]	82 [71–93]	100 [99–100]

[Krabbe et al. 2015](#)

Title: Aligning corporate greenhouse-gas emissions targets with climate goals

Author(s): Oskar Krabbe, Giel Linthorst, Kornelis Blok, Wina Crijns-Graus, Detlef P. van Vuuren, Niklas Höhne, Pedro Faria, Nate Aden and Alberto Carrillo Pineda

Description: A proposed method for corporate emissions target setting that derives carbon intensity pathways for companies based on sectoral pathways from existing mitigation scenarios:

Main Relevant Findings:

- It relates to **robustness and science-based target setting** as the carbon budgets of cities can use elements of how corporations set emissions targets.
- Sectoral emissions may be useful for setting goals at the city level - depending on what sector dominates a city. This could also be used as a counterfactual.
- **Corporate emissions target setting** based on **sectoral pathways from existing mitigation scenarios**: the Sectoral Decarbonization Approach (SDA). Sectoral emission pathways can be translated into sectoral intensity pathways (intensity pathway = emission pathway/activity) through physical indicators (e.g., tonnes of crude steel produced) or monetary indicators (e.g., value-added). As the ratio between energy use and physical indicators can be better related to emissions and mitigation potential, these indicators are preferable.
- Such indicators can only be used in sectors with one main product (for example, commodities such as cement, crude steel, and so on) or sectors where activity is relatively uniform (for example, passenger transportation by cars).
- One critical element is the projection of market share for a company. For 2050, its market share will of course be highly uncertain. However, in most cases targets will be set for much shorter time periods, for example, 5–15 yr ahead.
- The sum of all individual company emission targets does not exceed the entire sector's total carbon budget (as a condition)
- Intensity pathways were calculated so that the intensities of all steel companies converged to 2050 level.
- Limitations of SDA are the fact it does not include equity and there is a lack of data implications

[Kuriakose et al. 2022](#)

Title: What does the Paris Climate Change Agreement Mean for Local Policy? Downscaling the remaining global carbon budget to sub-national areas

Author(s): Jaise Kuriakose, Chris Jones, Kevin Anderson, Carly McLachlan, John Broderick

Description: The paper provides a relatively simple method for downscaling climate budgets from global to sub-national for the UK or potentially other post-industrial non-agricultural nations. Already has the numbers for many UK cities/regions. The paper also outlines the method used by the **Tyndal Local Carbon Budget Tool**.

Main Relevant Findings:

- The authors used **3 different national carbon budgets for the UK and downscaled** them to sub-national areas using 3 different allocations (i.e. equity) factors: Grandfathering (account for past emissions), Capability-based (based on Gross Value Added [GVA]) and Egalitarian-based (based on population).
- **Only CO₂ was used because there aren't IPCC budgets for the other gasses.** This is ok for the UK but not for a more agriculturally based nation
- **LULUCF** are considered neutral on a global scale and a global overhead for cement is subtracted before downscaling to a national scale.
- Sectors are also limited to energy use (power, heat, cooling, transport, and industry). **Aviation, Shipping, and Military** were subtracted from the national budget before downscaling
- **CDR** and offsets are not considered in the budget because of the lacking evidence, increasing vulnerability, and risk of undermining early action.

Main Relevant Findings:

- **Steps to follow in the figure below and key points for each step:**

1. Net zero targets and pledges, without a sequence of interim targets or cumulative accounting of emissions are unlikely to achieve Paris compliance. Additionally, a net zero framing risks deterring near-term mitigation through over-reliance on future carbon removal or carbon credits.
2. Differences in the properties of GHGs suggest that groups of gasses need to be treated differently, with the importance of this decision depending on the proportion of emissions of each gas within a given administrative boundary.
3. Uncertainty high about how much is left to reach a specific temperature target. A medium probability level is common, in particular for non-CO₂.
4. Decarbonization of some sectors takes longer. Some sectors may rather be a "global overhead" than the responsibility of one region (e.g., deforestation, cement).

5. Huge range when applying different equity concepts. Consequently, as with downscaling from global to national carbon budgets, allocation rules must be specified clearly when undertaking downscaling from national to sub-national levels.
 6. Uncertainties are high, all is a matter of real removal and international agreements.
- Grandfathering, as an allocation method, is determined to be more "appropriate" (i.e. realistic) than capability or egalitarian allocation methods with a decarbonization range of 7-16% reduction per year (for a 1.7-degree budget).
 - The 3 different national carbon budgets varied substantially. They included 2 budgets based on the IPCC carbon budgets for 1.5 (1150Mt) and 1.7 (2050Mt) and a carbon budget based on a balanced linear path to net zero carbon emissions by 2030 and 2050 (4611Mt).
 - **Net-zero targets with interim targets are considered bad because they are not directly connected to a temperature target** and can end up having a carbon budget 4x the budget associated with the 1.5-degree limit.
 - To date, more than 100 regional governments and 800 cities have made pledges to reach net zero by or before 2050
 - **Carbon budgets can be downscaled** to the national scale, as illustrated in the UK Climate Change Act (2008). Subsequently, they can be further downscaled to sub-national areas, as demonstrated in Scotland, and by Greater Manchester.
 - There are several initiatives that seek to facilitate sub-national climate change action, such as the Cities Race to Zero, Energy Cities, and the Science Based Targets Network.
 - Downscaling of global budgets is performed using the approach developed by Anderson et al. to post-2020 CO₂-only global budgets are chosen. The first, 700 GtCO₂, reflects a maximum mean surface temperature rise of 1.7 °C (for 66% distribution of TCRE₂), whilst the second, 650 GtCO₂, is associated with 1.5 °C (for 33% distribution of TCRE).
 - The results illustrate **wide variations in budgets between allocation regimes** and reflect a range of potential factors, including disparities in economic activity, population distribution between regions, and differences in per capita income compared to the national average.
 - The choice of factors for downscaling still further, from national to sub-national budgets, may exacerbate the implications of choosing between different national carbon budgets. Ostensibly choosing between simple allocation regimes within a country (e.g. egalitarian or capability) significantly impacts the mitigation action level required by sub-national regions and areas.
 - The energy sector and CO₂ focus okay if it comprises most of the emissions
 - Cooperation with the national government to target aviation sector emissions is needed

[Mirabella et al. 2022](#)

Title: Urban GHG accounting: discrepancies, constraints, and opportunities. Buildings and Cities

Author(s): Nadia Mirabella and Karen Allacker

Description: A comparison and critical analysis of three different GHG emission accounting standards: the Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GPC), Bilan Carbone, and ISO 14064-1:2018. The Organizational Environmental Footprint (OEF) and a previous analysis of footprinting performed by the European Commission are used as analytical lenses.

Main Relevant Findings

- Screen different methods using JRC Guidelines 2011 as a reference (SWOT; availability at city scale, the definition of city provided, LCT approach, system boundaries used, functional unit applied, source of inventory data, assessment of data quality, allocation rules used, identification of the responsible actor, type of impact assessment and GHGs accounted for, type of verification and reporting, and existence of ancillary tools)
 - a. System boundaries include: administrative approach, functional approach, and morphological approach; attribution of transboundary emissions: territorial/production based approach, supply chain/consumption-based approach; the question of whether accounting from consumers or producers perspective
 - b. Authors separate between net producers, net consumers, and floating producers-consumers
- The authors use a qualitative spider graph (time needed to perform the study, costs, network, communication, precision, accuracy, and complexity) scoring 0-3 according to high and low performance. It's a subjective judgment by the authors.

Main Relevant Findings:

- The paper can be used as a citation for the need to collaborate across disciplines and stakeholders (see discussion section)
- The challenges for city-level carbon accounting include 1) Setting system boundaries (also connected to the allocation of responsibility), 2) Having good data and expertise (connects to transparency), 3) Heterogeneity of reporting and verification (also links to language/terminology)
- None of the methods provides an in-depth discussion and proposal about the challenge of defining and categorizing the urban system in an appropriate way to serve a more efficient assessment and cross-city comparisons; including guidelines dealing with them.

- A set of a priori characteristics able to describe the specific city in terms of economic, social, historical, and geographical background could be beneficial (for comparison, for goals and scope definition, and for more strategic and efficient accounting process (cities could also be clustered according to their level of maturity for climate policies and their experience in this regard)
- Net producers are advised to use GPC, net exporters should complement (e.g., hybrid approach as in Ramaswami et al. 2008)
- Athanassiadis et al. 2016 found that urban GHG emissions estimated by the consumption-based approach in Brussels are more than 3 times higher than local measures indicate.
- Offers supplementary information online

Moran et al. 2018

Title: Carbon footprints of 13000 cities

Author(s): Daniel Moran, Keiichiro Kanemoto, Magnus Jiborn, Richard Wood, Johannes Többen and Karen C Seto

Description: Results from downscaling national Carbon Footprints (CFs) into a 250 m gridded model using data on population, purchasing power, and existing subnational CF studies from the US, China, EU, and Japan.

- Uses [MRIO data](#) (189 countries); subnational carbon footprints for USA, China, UK, Japan and Europe (data from various publications; national data are disaggregated to postal code zones); Worldbank, Eurostat and US BEA statistics for household spending; gridded pop (GHS-POP 250 m), per-capita purchasing power based on tax statistics. (Supplementary info: [data and model](#))
- To define cities the authors use EU Global Human Settlement Layer (*towns* are low-density clusters with ≥ 300 inhabitants km⁻² and min. 5000 people, *cities* are high-density clusters with ≥ 1500 i/km² and min. 50000; usually larger than city jurisdiction boundaries as they include urban fabric)

Figure 6. Types of urban areas: i. populous, high GDP with large footprints (Scope 3 exceeds Scope 1); ii. smaller, mid-GDP net embodied carbon importers (Scope 1 > Scope 3); iii. larger, low GDP producers (carbon exporters); and iv. smaller communities where predominantly Scope 3 > Scope 1.

- Uncertainties include the assumption that a rural dollar is as carbon-intense as an urban dollar; carbon intensities, purchasing power, and (governmental) non-household expenditure footprints are homogeneous within a region, direct emissions are evenly distributed; allocation and aggregation error up to 20% (see also Min & Rao 2017); MRIO up to 25% error

Main Relevant Findings:

- Urban centers have strong purchasing power and generate the majority of GDP; studies show that 50% of the variation in per-capita carbon footprint is explained by income and does not level off
- Top-down model GGMCF to estimate spatial distribution of urban carbon footprint with a gridded model (population, GDP), base year 2015; main predictors rural vs. urban consumption patterns and purchasing power
- The concentration of footprints are in a few urban centers
- Cities have jurisdiction over GHG emissions in the same magnitude as national governments
- The largest urban clusters almost all have carbon footprints in excess of their direct emissions;
- Mid-size urban areas with lower (higher) GDP are usually net exporters (importers, scope 1<scope 3)
- The top 5% wealthy suburban create 32% of respective rural emissions
- The current footprint hotspot cities are not the fastest growing

Nangini et al 2019

Title: A global dataset of CO2 emissions and ancillary data related to emissions for 343 cities

Author(s): Cathy Nangini, Anna Peregón, Philippe Ciais, Ulf Weddige, Felix Vogel, Jun Wang, François-Marie Bréon, Simeran Bachra, Yilong Wang, Kevin Gurney, Yoshiki Yamagata, Kyra Appleby, Sara Telahoun, Josep G. Canadell, Arnulf Grübler, Shobhakar Dhakal & Felix Creutzig

Description: A global dataset of Scope-1 city CO2 emissions based on CDP16, the carbonn Climate Registry of the Bonn Center for Local Climate Action and Reporting (<http://carbonn.org>), and a set of Chinese cities compiled by Beijing University (private communication).

Figure 1: Source datasets and their attributes.

Source datasets D^* and their attributes used to construct the final dataset D^{final} . Colors indicate type of dataset: brown (emissions), blue (socio-economic), gray (traffic-related), orange (climate-related).

Main Relevant Findings:

- Full traceability to the original data used in each city emission inventory is often not possible
- City-level CO₂ emissions and driver-related data are not always consistent across space and time.
- The scope of gasses and sectors covered by the datasets are often uneven and activity data could have been scaled down from national data when local activity data are unavailable.

Roelfsema et al. 2018

Title: Integrated assessment of international climate mitigation commitments outside the UNFCCC

Author(s): Mark Roelfsema, Mathijs Harmsen, Jos J.G. Olivier, Andries F. Hofa,, Detlef P. van Vuuren

Description: An assessment of the potential impact of Transnational Emission Reduction Initiatives (TERIs) on global GHG emissions using an Integrated Assessment Model (IAM).

Main Relevant Findings:

- The focus is on TERIs that existed before the Paris Agreement.
- TERIs can be important to ensuring and accelerating the implementation of mitigation measures. They can include a wide set of reduction measures, but often these overlap with reduction measures formulated by governments in the UNFCCC framework.

- The overlap in TERIs and pledges/NDCS is large and could become 70% by 2020 and 80% by 2030
- It relates to the **robustness & transparency** discussion.

Romero-Lankao et al. 2015

Title: Climate change: Track urban emissions on a human scale

Author(s): Kevin Robert Gurney, Paty Romero-Lankao, Karen C. Seto, Lucy R. Hutyra, Riley Duren, Christopher Kennedy, Nancy B. Grimm, James R. Ehleringer, Peter Marcotullio, Sara Hughes, Stephanie Pincetl, Mikhail V. Chester, Daniel M. Runfola, Johannes J. Feddema & Joshua Sperling

Description: An article advocating for the improvement of emissions tracking and collaboration between scientists and cities to make use of more fine-scale emission data.

Main Relevant Findings: The article mentions that **transparency of data and method** is crucial to enable comparisons and verification by third parties.

Sethi et al. 2020

Title: Climate change mitigation in cities: a systematic scoping of case studies

Author(s): Mahendra Sethi, William Lamb, Jan Minx and Felix Creutzig

Description: The authors utilize bibliometric methods and machine learning to meta-analyze 5635 urban case studies of climate change mitigation to assess the comparative characteristics of interventions (i.e. devising scientific models, climate plans, low-carbon strategies and development policies with climate co-benefits), including their relative efficacy, potentials and emissions reductions

- They undertake a systematic scoping review methodology involving the following steps: (a) clearly defining the research question; (b) systematically searching defined literature databases **for a defined time period**; (c) justifying and making a transparent selection of the literature; (d) assessing the quality of the selected evidence; and (e) synthesizing the evidence based on a clear and transparent method

Main Relevant Findings:

- We still have very little understanding of how well urban policy interventions work, under what conditions and why
- There are two pathways to systematize and scale up: 1) to develop data-based city typologies (combining data including remote sensing), and 2) evidence-driven synthesis starting with case studies to systematically compare and aggregate policy insights (e.g., to find spectrum of useful policies, to enable fast peer-to-peer learning)
- The clustering of cities is demonstrated by socio-demographics, industrial structure, urban form, local geography and climatic conditions (Brown et al 2008, Glaeser and Kahn 2010, Minx et al 2013, Baiocchiet al 2015)

- **Examining ex-post policy studies** for specificity of policy-governance instruments opted in different urban mitigation solutions
 - A review of ex-post studies underscores that a mix of market mechanisms, user incentives, subsidies, voluntary measures, etc in cooperation with non-governmental actors is crucial for local climate mitigation
 - The most studied sectors are building and transport
 - **Industry and waste sectors are the most isolated and need integration with the rest of urban functions through innovations and policy convergence** (e.g. enabling and voluntary measures are not at all observed in the waste sector)
 - Most of the urban solutions conform to enabling measures (46), regulatory instruments (45), voluntary, behavioral, awareness & education measures (37), followed by market/economic interventions (35).
 - There are very few examples where all policy instruments are simultaneously employed in urban climate solutions
 - Surprisingly, **initiatives** such as car-free cities, Fridays for future, odd–even car days, and congestion charges **that capture active public interest**, participation, and media attention **are missing in peer-reviewed scientific literature**, contrasting with the high mitigation potential.
 - For urban energy solutions, **supply-side policies** can be more effective if accompanied by participatory measures. **Demand-side interventions** are indispensable for urban climate mitigation.
 - **Effective transport sector policies:** municipal plans should provide facilities that encourage increased use of transportation alternatives, promote efficient vehicles and fuels, enable enhanced involvement of people towards sustainable travel behavior, smart parking systems, and greater public transit
 - Expanding of park area is cost effective and mitigation effective
 - **Urban mitigation across multiple sectors is scarce** and spans across buildings, energy & transport
 - **Plausible cross-cutting mitigation interventions** include the **municipal waste-industry:** demonstration of circular economy, biogas digestion, biomethanation & CO₂e certificates, **AFOLU/land and waste:** landfill site restoration to expand green cover and GHG mitigation, **Energy-transport:** Instruments for bulk-purchase of green energy by transport companies, **Building-energy:** Power purchase agreements between renewable energy plants, regional power grid, local electricity distribution companies on one end and townships, special zones, municipal councils, residential communities including prosumers on the other, and **Ecocity/smart city developments:** Integrated planned solutions encompassing solar PV, building EE measures, E-mobility, WTE and/or other combinations of the above interventions.
- **In urban climate literature, mitigation options that are frequently studied are not necessarily those with the highest potential**
- **Expanding extra-regulatory and non-governmental actions is imperative in local climate governance**
- **The resultant mitigation potential (in %) of combining two urban interventions is greater than the net sum of individual interventions.**

[Sporchia et al. 2022](#)

Title: Sub-National Scale Initiatives for Climate Change Mitigation: Refining the Approach to Increase the Effectiveness of the Covenant of Mayors

Author(s): Fabio Sporchia, Michela Marchi, Enrico Nocentini, Nadia Marchettini and Federico Maria Pulselli

Description: A case study where the authors compare the reported emissions of the Municipality of Grosseto using the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy (GCoM) guidelines and the reported emissions using the IPCC's methods.

Main Relevant Findings:

- The GCoMs method leaves out or marks optional important sectors (IPPU and AFOLU) and gasses (NO₂ and CH₄) limiting municipalities in their ability to address these emission sources.
- Integrating these approaches is feasible and doesn't require new calculations but does require an intermediate passage to recategorize the IPCC sectors to match and expand upon the GCoM sectors.
- This is especially important for municipalities like Grosseto that are more agricultural-based (e.g. both emissions and sequestration from AFOLU can have a large impact on the emissions makeup and can encourage mitigation/adaptation approaches such as nature-based solutions)
 - In Grosseto ~17% of CO₂ emissions were covered by vegetation fixation.
 - Grosseto's emissions were underestimated by the GCoM inventory by 9% in comparison to the IPCC-based inventory

[Steininger et al.](#)

Title: Multiple carbon accounting to support just and effective climate policies

Author(s): Karl W. Steininger, Christian Lininger, Lukas H. Meyer, Pablo Muñoz & Thomas Schinko

Description: An analysis of several distinct types of national carbon accounts and accounting methods

Main Relevant Findings: None of the accounting systems, however, prove 'best' in supporting effective and just climate policy under real-world circumstances. Thus it's suggested to compile reliable data to aid in the consistent calculation of multiple carbon accounts on a global level.

[Sudmant et al. 2018](#)

Title: Producer cities and consumer cities: Using production- and consumption-based carbon accounts to guide climate action in China, the UK, and the US

Author(s): Andrew Sudmant, Andy Gouldson, Joel Millward-Hopkins, Kate Scott and John Barrett

Description: An analysis and comparison of production- and consumption-based emissions accounts for urban centers in China, the UK, and the US

Main Relevant Findings:

- The extent that urban activities and metrics can be linked with emissions informs the extent that these activities and metrics can be used to inform policy-making.
- **Consumer urban areas** out-source more emissions than they in-source and those that in-source more than they out-source are referred to as **producer urban areas**
- **Relationships between urban income and emissions:**
 - approximately 1/3 of the variation in per capita production emissions can be explained for by income
 - more than 80% of the variation in consumption emissions is explained by differences in income (similar strong relationship for net emissions vs. income)
 - finding suggests that rising incomes not only lead to rising demand for goods and services, but that demand is met by imports, rather than local production
 - urban consumption-based emissions per capita against urban population density - negative correlation explaining approximately 75% of the variation in emissions
 - suggests that energy use declines with density
- A **consumption-based approach** to urban emissions therefore highlights the importance of income and density, and raises the concern that these metrics are receiving relatively less attention than they **merit** in informing urban actions.
- Analysis illustrates that urban characteristics, much more than the country in which urban areas are located, describe the structure of urban emissions. While urban areas in this analysis tend to cluster by country, **urban characteristics are much better predictors of emissions.**
- Common opportunities for climate mitigation across urban areas with particular characteristics, including megacities (He et al., 2016), rapidly growing developing and middle-income cities (Colenbrander et al., 2015, 2016), and urban areas with other specific characteristics (Gouldson et al., 2015; Sudmant et al., 2015), have been **well established in the literature.**
- urban areas: less power of admin to set taxes etc. but they are close to local stakeholders.
- **It may be in the hands of cities to...**
 - Introduce product and resource efficiency standards which can significantly impact on embedded emissions
 - Add refundable recycling fees to a wide range of goods
 - Incentivize reductions in final demand through changes in urban planning (urban form, urban function).
 - Achieve deep levels of decarbonisation especially those **compatible with** limiting average global warming levels to **1.5 C**, are likely to demand that urban areas **pursue both production- and consumption-based approaches - lack of research here**

SR15

Title: Mitigation Pathways Compatible with 1.5°C in the Context of Sustainable Development
Author(s): IPCC Lead Authors - Solomon Ffita, Piers Forster), Veronika Ginzburg, Collins Handa, Haroon Khesghi, Shigeki Kobayashi, Elmar Kriegler, Luis Mundaca, Roland Séférian, and Maria Virginia Vilariño

Description: An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty

Main Relevant Findings:

- **Defines remaining carbon budget** (Section 2.2.2.2): "... AR5 ... approximately 400 GtCO₂ for the 1.5°C budget (66% of model simulations). In contrast, this assessment finds approximately 860 GtCO₂ for the 1.5°C budget (66th TCRE percentile). .. medium confidence can be assigned to the assessed remaining budget values for 1.5°C ... and ... uncertainty". The uncertainties presented in Table 2.2 cannot be formally combined, but current understanding of the assessed geophysical uncertainties suggests at least a ±50% possible variation for remaining carbon budgets for 1.5°C-consistent pathways.
- **Explores the feasibility for 1.5 with global IAM** (Section 2.3.1.1): "... No model found a 1.5°C-consistent pathway (abbreviated: cp) for SSP3 and some models could not identify 1.5°C-cp for SSP5 ... effective control of land-use emissions becomes even more critical ... Due to high inequality levels in SSP4, land use can be less well managed ... causing 2 of 3 models to no longer find an SSP4-based 1.5°C-cp. ... Six participating models identified 1.5°C-cp in.. SP1 .. and 4/6 six models found 1.5°C-cp for ... SSP2."
- Defines classes of scenarios. (**OPCC refers to 1.5-low-OS scenarios**)

Table 2.SM.11: Overview of pathway class specifications

Pathway group	Class name	Short name combined classes	MAGICC exceedance probability filter	Number of scenarios
1.5°C	Below 1.5°C	-	$P(1.5^\circ\text{C}) \leq 0.34$	0
	Below 1.5°C	Below-1.5°C	$0.34 < P(1.5^\circ\text{C}) \leq 0.5$	9
	1.5°C Return with low OS	1.5°C-low-OS	$0.5 < P(1.5^\circ\text{C}) \leq 0.67$ AND $P(1.5^\circ\text{C in 2100}) \leq 0.5$	34
			$0.5 < P(1.5^\circ\text{C}) \leq 0.67$ AND $0.34 < P(1.5^\circ\text{C in 2100}) \leq 0.5$	10
	1.5°C Return with high OS	1.5°C-high-OS	$0.67 < P(1.5^\circ\text{C})$ AND $P(1.5^\circ\text{C in 2100}) \leq 0.34$	19
			$0.67 < P(1.5^\circ\text{C})$ AND $0.34 < P(1.5^\circ\text{C in 2100}) \leq 0.5$	18
2°C	Lower 2°C	Lower-2°C	$P(2^\circ\text{C}) \leq 0.34$ (excluding above)	74
	Higher 2°C	Higher-2°C	$0.34 < P(2^\circ\text{C}) \leq 0.5$ (excluding above)	58
	Above 2°C	-	$0.5 < P(2^\circ\text{C})$	189

As noted in the chapter text, scenario classification was based on probabilistic temperature outcomes assessed using the AR5 assessment of composition, forcing and climate response. These were represented within the MAGICC model (Meinshausen et al., 2009, 2011a) which was used in the same setup as AR5 WGIII analyses. As discussed in Section 2.2, updates in geophysical understanding would alter such results were they incorporated within MAGICC, though central outcomes would remain well within the probability distribution of the setup used here (see Section 2.SM.1.1).

- Finds that for the 1.5-low-OS scenario that "Pathways limiting median warming to below 1.5°C in 2100 and with a 50–67% probability of temporarily overshooting that level earlier, generally implying less than 0.1°C higher peak warming than Below-1.5°C pathways" (see

Table 2.1) and "For instance, median aggregated 2030 GHG emissions are about 10 GtCO₂e yr⁻¹ lower in 1.5°C-low-OS compared to 1.5°C-highOS pathways, with respective interquartile ranges of 26–31 and 36–49 GtCO₂e yr⁻¹ (Table 2.4). These ranges correspond to about 25–30 and 35–48 GtCO₂e yr⁻¹ in 2030, respectively, when aggregated with 100-year Global Warming Potentials from the IPCC Second Assessment Report." (See table 2.1 below)

- See below, the statement about the timing of global zero emissions in SR1.5., Table 2.4

Table 2.4 | Emissions in 2030, 2050 and 2100 in 1.5°C and 2°C scenario classes and absolute annual rates of change between 2010–2030, 2020–2030 and 2030–2050, respectively.

Values show median and interquartile range across available scenarios (25th and 75th percentile given in brackets). If fewer than seven scenarios are available (*), the minimum–maximum range is given instead. Kyoto-GHG emissions are aggregated with GWP-100 values from IPCC AR4. Emissions in 2010 for total net CO₂, CO₂ from fossil-fuel use and industry, and AFOLU CO₂ are estimated at 38.5, 33.4, and 5 GtCO₂yr⁻¹, respectively (LeQuéré et al., 2018). Percentage reduction numbers included in headline statement C.1 in the Summary for Policymakers are computed relative to 2010 emissions in each individual pathway, and hence differ slightly from a case where reductions are computed relative to the historical 2010 emissions reported above. A difference is reported in estimating the 'anthropogenic' sink by countries or the global carbon modelling community (Grassi et al., 2017), and AFOLU CO₂ estimates reported here are thus not necessarily comparable with countries' estimates. Scenarios with year-2010 Kyoto-GHG emissions outside the range assessed by IPCC AR5 WGIII are excluded (IPCC, 2014b), as are scenario duplicates that would bias ranges towards a single study.

Name	Category	#	Annual emissions/sequestration (GtCO ₂ yr ⁻¹)			Absolute Annual Change (GtCO ₂ /yr ⁻¹)			Timing of Global Zero
			2030	2050	2100	2010–2030	2020–2030	2030–2050	Year
Total CO ₂ (net)	Below-1.5°C	5*	13.4 (15.4, 11.4)	-3.0 (1.7, -10.6)	-8.0 (-2.6, -14.2)	-1.2 (-1.0, -1.3)	-2.5 (-1.8, -2.8)	-0.8 (-0.7, -1.2)	2044 (2037, 2054)
	1.5°C-low-OS	37	20.8 (22.2, 18.0)	-0.4 (2.7, -2.0)	-10.8 (-8.1, -14.3)	-0.8 (-0.7, -1.0)	-1.7 (-1.4, -2.3)	-1.0 (-0.8, -1.2)	2050 (2047, 2055)
	1.5°C with no or limited OS	42	20.3 (22.0, 15.9)	-0.5 (2.2, -2.8)	-10.2 (-7.6, -14.2)	-0.9 (-0.7, -1.1)	-1.8 (-1.5, -2.3)	-1.0 (-0.8, -1.2)	2050 (2046, 2055)
	1.5°C-high-OS	36	29.1 (36.4, 26.0)	1.0 (6.3, -1.2)	-13.8 (-11.1, -16.4)	-0.4 (0.0, -0.6)	-1.1 (-0.5, -1.5)	-1.3 (-1.1, -1.8)	2052 (2049, 2059)
	Lower-2°C	54	28.9 (33.7, 24.5)	9.9 (13.1, 6.5)	-5.1 (-2.6, -10.3)	-0.4 (-0.2, -0.6)	-1.1 (-0.8, -1.6)	-0.9 (-0.8, -1.2)	2070 (2063, 2079)
Higher-2°C	54	33.5 (35.0, 31.0)	17.9 (19.1, 12.2)	-3.3 (0.6, -11.5)	-0.2 (-0.0, -0.4)	-0.7 (-0.5, -0.9)	-0.8 (-0.6, -1.0)	2085 (2070, post-2100)	

Table 2.1 | Classification of pathways that this chapter draws upon, along with the number of available pathways in each class. The definition of each class is based on probabilities derived from the MAGICC model in a setup identical to AR5 WGIII (Clarke et al., 2014), as detailed in Supplementary Material 2.SM.1.4.

Pathway group	Pathway Class	Pathway Selection Criteria and Description	Number of Scenarios	Number of Scenarios
1.5°C or 1.5°C-consistent**	Below-1.5°C	Pathways limiting peak warming to below 1.5°C during the entire 21st century with 50–66% likelihood*	9	90
	1.5°C-low-OS	Pathways limiting median warming to below 1.5°C in 2100 and with a 50–67% probability of temporarily overshooting that level earlier, generally implying less than 0.1°C higher peak warming than Below-1.5°C pathways	44	
	1.5°C-high-OS	Pathways limiting median warming to below 1.5°C in 2100 and with a greater than 67% probability of temporarily overshooting that level earlier, generally implying 0.1–0.4°C higher peak warming than Below-1.5°C pathways	37	
2°C or 2°C-consistent	Lower-2°C	Pathways limiting peak warming to below 2°C during the entire 21st century with greater than 66% likelihood	74	132
	Higher-2°C	Pathways assessed to keep peak warming to below 2°C during the entire 21st century with 50–66% likelihood	58	

* No pathways were available that achieve a greater than 66% probability of limiting warming below 1.5°C during the entire 21st century based on the MAGICC model projections.

** This chapter uses the term 1.5°C-consistent pathways to refer to pathways with no overshoot, with limited (low) overshoot, and with high overshoot. However, the Summary for Policymakers focusses on pathways with no or limited (low) overshoot.

Ürge-Vorsatz et al. 2018

Title: Locking in positive climate responses in cities

Author(s): Diana Ürge-Vorsatz, Cynthia Rosenzweig, Richard J. Dawson, Roberto Sanchez Rodriguez, Xuemei Bai, Aliyu Salisu Barau, Karen C. Seto & Shobhakar Dhakal

Description: A commentary on lock-ins and a call for integrated action planning

Main Relevant Findings:

- The paper has a list of mitigation vs. adaptation interdependencies (Fig. 1) and a list of positive, neutral and negative lock-ins for 3 classes (institutional, behavioral and infrastructural lock-ins) (Fig. 2) which could be of use.

Legend:

industry located outside of the city	
final demand outside of the city	
emissions embodied in final products	
emissions embodied in intermediate products	

Wiedmann et al. 2020

Title: Scientists' warning on affluence

Author(s): Thomas Wiedmann, Manfred Lenzen, Lorenz T. Keyßer & Julia K. Steinberger

Description: A summary and presentation of evidence around the link between affluence and increased resource use and pollutant emissions as well as a presentation of possible solution approaches.

Main Relevant Findings:

- Existing societies, economies, and cultures incite consumption expansion, and the structural imperative for growth in competitive market economies inhibits necessary societal change
- Any transition towards sustainability can only be effective if far-reaching lifestyle changes complement technological advancements.

Methods and Gray Literature

Here we review reports and guidelines on different methods used to determine emissions targets for subnational targets. We start with the three methods of interest identified by SBTN (Deadline 2020, One Planet City Challenge, and The Tyndall Local Carbon Budget Tool), then proceed to review other methods and tools used for subnational target setting.

Method 1: Deadline 2020

Summary Table:

Deadline 2020 (2016)	
City coverage	84 C40 cities as of 2016
City typologies	<p>Four city typologies based on two distinct thresholds of GHG/capita and GDPppp/capita</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early peaker • Late peaker • Steady decliner • Steep decliner
C40 Cities pathways aligned with 1.5°C	C40 Cities Carbon Budget for 1.5°C and 2°C calculated using <i>contraction and convergence</i> approach for 2030 and common decline to 2050
Approach to ensure alignment of aggregated city-level pathways with C40 Cities pathways	Aggregation of city-level pathways for 1.5°C of global warming (total of 51 GtCO ₂ e by 2050) matches C40 Cities Carbon Budget of 22 GtCO ₂ e up to 2100 and assumed emission removals of 31 GtCO ₂ e up to 2100
Relation to Verification Principles (Target Setting)	<p>Science-Based: As the plan was for 2020, it's hard to update with the latest research past 2020. The report uses AR5 in developing its carbon budget.</p> <p>Equity: A linear contraction and convergence method using emissions per capita is used to determine the share of the global carbon budget that is assigned to the C40 cities.</p> <p>C40 cities are also divided into four trajectory groups based on emissions, GDP, and expected population growth to determine the carbon trajectory required for each city.</p> <p>Robustness & Transparency: The baseline emissions data used included total territorial scope 1 and 2 GHG emissions in CO₂e and the proportional split of those emissions across five sectors: Stationary energy, transport, waste, AFOLU, IPPU (industrial process and product use). The GPC inventories include the seven gasses covered by the UNFCCC6 namely CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, hydrofluorocarbons, perfluorocarbons, SF₆ and NF₃.</p> <p>Transparency is low compared to the other methods as much of the data and calculations are not available to the public.</p> <p>Applicability & Ease of Use: 2CAP model developed to project each city's target trajectory and dispatches actions.</p> <p>Practical & Context Relevant: Focused on 2020 and we have already passed this deadline</p>

<p>Relation to Verification Principles (Action Planning)</p>	<p>Science-Based: CAPs must: set an ambitious interim (e.g. 2030) and long-term (2050) target or budget to be emissions neutral by 2050 in line with Paris Agreement; detail governance powers and capacity and partners needed to deliver goals; integrate adaptation and mitigation; be transformational and evidence-based; and consider relevant national and subnational commitments (inter-governmental consideration). Goals should: be based on climate change scenarios and hazard/risk assessments</p> <p>Equity: CAPs must engage with community/stakeholders and have a communications plan to inform the plan and ensure equitable distribution of benefits to the city's population. They should provide short-term detail and long-term direction. CAP should cater communication efforts to inform "hard to reach" groups, co-design with stakeholders, have materials translated to commonly spoken languages and international audiences.</p> <p>Robustness & Transparency: CAPs must have a transparent process to monitor delivery, communicate progress, and be updated in line with government reporting systems. It is advised to report to a common global platform to communicate contributions. Actions should reference the evidence-base including an emissions inventory, scenario modeling, climate risk assessment, and socio-economic context. Scopes must include: Scope 1, Scope 2, treatment of waste within the city boundary (scope 1 & 3), and when possible consumption-based (scope 3). Also residual emissions should be identified by 2050. CAPs must include <i>key sectors</i> (e.g. energy, building, transport, and waste). Sector-level inventories must be referenced and include a full year of data, scopes mentioned above as well as IPPU and AFOLU if the city's economy has strong contribution. Emissions scenarios must take into account projected population and economic changes and include a BAU scenario.</p> <p>Applicability & Ease of Use: Support for cities includes: Climate Action Planning (CAP) Framework, technical assistance program which includes a range of resources, guidance, tools, peer-to-peer knowledge sharing, and direct assistance for C40 members. An email is provided for further information and assistance. Terms are well defined (e.g. Transformation, Emissions Neutral, Ambitious, etc.)</p> <p>Practical & Context Relevant: Requires written commitment from mayors or city leaders to begin implementing transformational and inclusive action for emissions neutral 2050, consistent with the Paris Agreement. CAPs must describe administrative boundaries, physical geography, socioeconomic priorities, availability/access, affordability/prosperity, spatial inclusion aspects, and governance structure. CAPs are advised to describe the environmental quality and indicators, city infrastructure and systems, economic growth, future trends, relation to SDGs and critical assets or functions.</p>
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Analysis

The Deadline 2020 (D2020) report first derives a budget for C40 cities altogether using a contraction and convergence allocation approach. This approach is not considered fair but is here justified by the fact that C40 cities are located in both developing and developed countries and are thus similar to the rest of the world. This approach is also affecting the equity of the results as cities are normally wealthier and having lower per capita emissions than rural areas. Importantly, the C40 emissions budget derived here is not met by the sum of C40 cities' emissions trajectories. Indeed, city level emissions trajectories are calculated in a bottom up manner and are not bounded by a total budget. As a result, the C40 budget is greatly overshot. Cities are first categorized on the basis of their GDR_{ppp}/capita and each of the four categories entails a specific formula that defines the emissions allocation of the city starting at today's emissions levels.

The deadline 2020 uses equity, amongst other considerations to derive city level emissions targets but ultimately presents the emissions allocations, and thus emissions target as domestic. As a result of this modeling choice, the implementation of equity considerations is bound to provide some perceived implementation realism. This comes at the cost of equity and ambition. The budget overshoot is not discussed and the city trajectories are not part of an additive approach that can compare 2030 emissions to IPCC global recommendation. It is hard to relate the cities' allocations to the global effort needed to meet the Paris goal.

[C40 Deadline 2020 \(2016\)](#)

Title: Deadline 2020: How Cities Will Get the Job Done (2016)

Author(s): C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group and ARUP

Description: The document is a call for C40 cities to take climate action by 2020 which outlines pathways for C40 cities, detailing target setting and actions cities need to take to meet the temperature targets of the Paris Agreement.

Method:

- **Step 1 develops a global carbon budget** out to 2100 for 1.5 and 2 degree temperature rise scenarios.
 - The global GHG budget from 1870-2100 is calculated to be 387 GtCO₂
- **Step 2 estimates what the 'fair share' of the remaining global budget** should be for the 84 C40 cities.
 - This budget is calculated using linear **contraction and convergence**: assuming cities' per capita emissions (and those of the rest of the world) converge linearly to a common value, then everyone declines to zero at a common rate depending on the remaining budget.
 - The baseline year is 2015 and **covers scope 1 and 2** of GHG in CO₂e, not scope 3 (due to lack of data and risk of double-counting)
 - This results gives a budget of 22 GtCO₂e to C40 cities (6% of the global budget to 2100)
 - **Average emissions per capita for the 84 cities is 5tCO₂e which, the report concludes, must be reduced to 2.9 tCO₂e by 2030** to meet the temperature goals of the Paris Agreement.
- **Step 3 assigns one four per capita emissions reduction trajectory typologies** based on each city's current emissions per capita and GDP per capita. The characteristics of these four trajectories are flexed to share the burden between cities and achieve rapid emissions reductions across cities.

- Trajectories, criteria and the number of cities per trajectory can be seen in the figure below:

- **Step 4** Outlines some of the city-specific **action pathways necessary to meet the target trajectories**, laying out the pace, scale and prioritization of action needed between 2016 and 2100
 - The 2CAP model is used to investigate the actions required by cities, and the external factors (such as electrical grid decarbonisation) necessary to achieve each city's target trajectory

Report Results and Conclusions

- From 2016 - 2050, over \$1 trillion is required across C40 cities to meet the ambition of the Paris Agreement
- Mayors can deliver or influence just over half of the savings needed to put C40 cities on a 1.5 degree trajectory
- Action is needed from 2023 at the latest to meet Paris Agreement temperature targets

Deadline 2020 Method Report (2016)

Title: Deadline 2020: Method Report (2016)

Author(s): C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group and ARUP

Description: The document provides more details on the methodology behind the Deadline 2020 report. It discusses, more in-depth, the seven methodologies for allocating a carbon budget.

Data Source and Calculation Details

- **Baseline City Emissions**
 - The baseline emissions included scope 1 and 2 GHG emissions in CO₂e for the year 2015 split across five sectors: Stationary Energy, Transport, Waste, AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and other Land Use), and IPPU (Industrial Process and Product Use)

- Emissions data was sourced from inventories for the Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GPC) or the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), prioritizing GPC as it has higher sectoral resolution.
- The reporting year of emissions data ranged from 2009 to 2016. Data was normalized to the year 2015 using city-based Gross Regional Product (GRP) growth rate projections sourced from the Economist Intelligence Unit (2016).
- Cities that had emissions data from either source were considered “Primary” cities and those that didn’t have data were considered “Secondary” cities and a process of “mapping” these cities to the most similar Primary city using 11 criteria.
 - The mapping criteria were weighed based on assessed importance in the following order (points in parentheses): country (5), region (4) , city GRP/cap (4), continent (3), climate zone (3), HDI (3), pop growth in 2015 (2), GRP growth rate in 2015 (2), GRP absolute in 2015 (1), population density (2), and population in 2015 (1).
 - The maximum points for matching is 30, with the higher points resulting in a better match for mapping.
 - Once a Primary-Secondary city pairing was made, the total per-capita emissions of the Primary city were multiplied by the population of the Secondary city to produce the total baseline territorial emissions of the Secondary city.
 - The sector proportions (in percentages across the five sectors mentioned above) of the Primary city were also replicated for the Secondary city.
 -
- City-specific emissions inventories were available for 47 (of 84) cities, 25 of which came from the GPC database and 22 from CDP.
- **Global Carbon Budget**
 - Budgets were chosen based on their ability to fulfill the following criteria:
 - Must include all GHGs
 - Must include all anthropogenic emissions from all possible sources.
 - Good chance of meeting the target temperature. (66% or higher chance)
 - Extended out to 2100.
 - Global carbon budgets were derived from the following sources:
 - IPCC AR5 Synthesis Report, Table 2.2 page 64
 - IPCC AR5 WGI, page 27
 - The remaining budgets for the period between 2015 and 2100 was calculated by subtracting the cumulative GHG emissions thus far (1870-2015) given by the IPCC, Emissions Data for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR), and Le Queré (2015).
- **Global Budget Allocation (fairness)**
 - A focused literature was done on fair allocation of the global carbon budget focused on the following sources
 - A joint paper by The Centre for Climate Change Economics and Policy (CCCEP) and The Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment – (Averchenkova et al, 2014)

- WWF Australia commissioned a report by Ecofys on Australia’s carbon budget based on global effort sharing. (Ecofys, 2013) The proposed methodologies were used to advise South Africa as well. (WWF, 2014)
 - Concordia University (Gignac and Matthews, 2015)
 - The principles of Equality, Responsibility and Capacity were considered when considering fairness and the following approaches were examined:
 - **Grandfathering** - The budget is distributed based on a region’s current shares of global emissions.
 - **Carbon Space** - an equal share of the remaining global budget based on per capita emissions.
 - **Blended sharing** - a combination of the above methods with a moderating factor to try and find a compromise between practicality and responsibility.
 - **Contraction and Convergence** - an equal global per capita emissions target is set in the future (between 2020-2050) and once reached a linear trajectory to net zero is followed (i.e. using the carbon space method). This approach is arguably less effective than the carbon spaced approach in responding to principle 2 and 3 as a result of this delayed convergence.
 - **Common but Differentiated Convergence** - a variation on Contraction and Convergence wherein linear convergence starts from the year a threshold percentage of global emissions per capita is reached.
 - **Cost Proportional to City GRP per Capita** - all cities are made to contribute an equal percentage of their GRP towards the total mitigation cost.
 - **Equal Marginal Cost** - This approach is not influenced by any ethical principles, instead relying on regional marginal abatement costs for assigning where mitigation should occur and by implication the nation or region responsible for implementing the recommended actions.
 - Contraction and Convergence was chosen, with a convergence date of 2030, using an internal scoring matrix
- **City Emission Reduction Trajectories**
 - BAU trajectories were developed using the Kaya Identity taking population, city GRP per capita and energy per unit city GRP, were projected based on moderate forecasts from sources including the UN (2015), Economist Intelligence Unit (2016) and IPCC(2014). Carbon intensity was assumed to remain constant.
 - Cities were given one of four trajectories based on their current emissions per capita and city GRP as shown in the figures below.

Table 9. Examples of process for assigning city typology. Cities marked with * reported via CDP.

GHG/Capita	City GRP/capita	Assigned typology	Example cities
High (>5.1 tCO ₂ e/capita)	High (>\$15,000/capita)	<i>Steep Decline</i>	<i>Toronto Melbourne New York City</i>
	Low (<\$15,000/capita)	<i>Early Peak</i>	<i>Cape Town Durban*</i>
Low (<5.1 tCO ₂ e/capita)	High (>\$15,000/capita)	<i>Steady Decline</i>	<i>Stockholm Seoul* London</i>
	Low (<\$15,000/capita)	<i>Late Peak</i>	<i>Quito Caracas* Amman</i>

Table 10: Peak years assigned for city typologies. *i.e. these cities must already have peaked.

Trajectory	Peak Year	Trend up to peak year	Rate of emissions decrease
Steady decline	2016*	n/a	Steady
Steep decline	2016*	n/a	Steep
Early Peak	2020	Linear increase	Steady post peak year
Late Peak	2025	Linear increase	Steady post peak year

- All city emissions trajectories were modeled with logistic growth functions (S-Curves) and a mathematical function that governs the overall shape of the trajectory which considers the following factors:
 - Allowing peaking cities to increase their emissions on a per capita basis either meant they had to peak very soon or declining cities had to reduce emissions at a very fast rate.
 - A balance between allowing developing cities sufficient time before peaking/reductions are required and not assigning unrealistic reduction rates to developed cities.
 - Final trajectories needed to have a plausible year-on-year reduction rate. The maximum limit used to develop these trajectories was a 20% annual reduction.
- Absolute emissions trajectories were obtained by multiplying the annual emissions per capita by population growth in the corresponding year.
- **City Specific Action Pathways**
 - The C40-Arup Partnership Climate Action Pathways (2CAP) model was made to develop an action pathway for each C40 city to meet the target climate safe trajectory developed out of the trajectory analysis.
 - Inputs included:
 - Modeled climate safe per capita emissions trajectories per city
 - BAU per capita emissions trajectories per city to 2100
 - City baseline action data (adaptation actions are not included)
 - Individual Action criteria (i.e. impact, roll-out time, program allocation, replicability, cost, etc.)

D2020 Climate Action Planning Framework

Title: Climate Action Planning Framework (2020)

Author(s): C40 Cities and Pilot Cities (see below)

Description: C40's guide for cities to create a Climate Action Plan (CAP) that is aligned with the Paris Agreement. The framework outlines what is essential vs suggested in a city's CAP to be considered a C40 participant. The framework combines technical assistance for C40 cities.

General Notes:

- The document is an updated expansion to the Climate Action Planning Framework focused on developing Climate Action Plans (CAPs) and is broken into 3 pillars: (1) Commitment and Collaboration, (2) Challenges and Opportunities, (3) Acceleration and implementation
- It includes standards for: setting targets/budgets and pathways for emissions neutrality by 2050, improving adaptation and resilience based on climate risk assessments, engaging communities and stakeholders to ensure equity, outlining governance powers, capacity, and partners needed, and considering relevant national or subnational commitments.
- Development processes

- The framework was developed in collaboration with the cities that participated in C40's Climate Action Planning pilot programme (Boston, Durban, London, Los Angeles, Melbourne, Mexico City, New York City and Paris).
- The development process ran throughout 2017-18 (same time as the cities in the pilot programme were updating their climate action plans).
- The framework has been peer-reviewed by key external organizations dedicated to climate change, adaptation and achieving the objectives of the Paris Agreement.
- Further revisions were made in March 2020 based on learning from the deployment of the CAP Framework across C40 member cities.

Method 2: One Planet City Challenge

Summary Table:

Deadline 2020 (2016)	
City coverage	400 cities have participated as of 2019
City typologies	Cities are not categorized into typologies. National HDIs are used when calculating targets to account for their differences (e.g. health, knowledge, standard of living)
Cities pathways aligned with 1.5°C	<p>The OPCC uses scenarios from the IAMC 1.5 Scenario explorer that are classified as "1.5C Return with low overshoot (OS)" or short "1.5C-low-OS" (see Supplementary Material for Chapter 2, Table 2.SM.11)</p> <p>They conclude the following targets meet the Paris Agreement given the latest science.</p> <p>2030: Reducing per capita emissions in-line with a global reduction of 50%</p> <p>2050: Reducing total emissions to net zero</p>
Relation to Verification Principles (Target Setting)	<p>Science-Based: The report uses SR1.5 in developing its paris compliant targets.</p> <p>Equity: National HDIs are factored into calculating the decarbonization target. A reduction factor is created using HDIs wherein cities from high HDI countries must decarbonize faster than cities from low HDI countries. As a result, prescribed 2030 targets range between 25-65% reductions depending on development levels as determined by the HDI.</p> <p>Robustness & Transparency: OPCC requires cities to have a mid-term and a long-term target for Scope 1 and 2 emissions. They encourage leading cities to include Scope 3 in their reporting and engage with residents to address these emissions.</p> <p>All 7 GHGs are considered when scoring city inventories</p> <p>Applicability & Ease of Use: The instructions on target setting are laid out clearly step by step.</p> <p>Practical & Context Relevant: There have been several updates to the Assessment Framework which have incorporated new approaches/scoring/criteria which demonstrates that it is a flexible method.</p>
Relation to Verification	Science-Based: A C40 and McKinsey report, for C40 cities to achieve 90% emissions reductions by 2050, guides the feedback for mitigation based on six city typologies.

<p>Principles (Action Planning)</p>	<p>Equity: A GDP-emphasized city typology categorization (adapted from the D2020 city categorizations) adds a capacity element to the scoring and feedback cities receive in the OPCC.</p> <p>Robustness and Transparency: A list of indicators along with the scoring criteria and weights applied is included in the framework which clarifies the criteria being measured for the pre-screening process of OPCC.</p> <p>Applicability & Ease of Use: The criteria for high scoring climate action are laid out clearly in the scoring criteria and indicators in the report.</p> <p>Practical & Context Relevant: There have been several updates to the Assessment Framework which have incorporated new approaches/scoring/criteria which demonstrates that it is a flexible method. They also indicate places where they foresee changes as research develops (e.g. consumption-based accounting).</p>
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WWF - One Planet City Challenge (2019)

Title: One Planet City Challenge (2019) - Updated Assessment Framework

Author(s): World Wildlife Fund (WWF) and ARUP

Description: The document was designed to provide local governments with an updated in-depth explanation of the One Planet City Challenge (OPCC) Assessment Framework as well as guidance on target setting, GHG inventory reporting, and climate action planning.

OPCC Overview

- The One Planet City Challenge (OPCC) is a biennial competition organized by WWF to encourage candidate cities to take climate action. Candidate cities are guided to **ensure alignment with the Paris Agreement ambitions, demonstrate that they are progressing in accordance with their fair share of the global carbon budget, have targets that align with an appropriate decarbonisation trajectory** and are undertaking **evidence-based climate action planning**.

Figure 1. Outline of the 2019-2020 OPCC Cycle.

- The competition itself has 5 stages seen in the figure above.
- 400 candidate cities from 25 countries on 5 continents had participated at least once

Competition Criteria

- The jury of competition evaluators focus on the following criteria to judge each city candidate:
 - **Commitments** (political), **targets and goals** (mitigation and adaptation), **evidence for action planning** (emissions reporting, risk/vulnerability assessments), and **climate and adaptation action plans** (mitigation and adaptation).
 - Shortlisted city assessment includes the above categories in more detail as well as **monitoring, reporting, evaluation, communication, outreach, and advocacy**.
 - In order to score high in these categories, candidate cities need:
 - A clear commitment to tackle the effects of climate change, including the backing of the mayor or council, and dedicated resources for climate action;
 - Ambitious mitigation and adaptation targets for both the mid-term and the long-term;
 - Evidence-based action planning that shows engagement with a broad set of stakeholders, assesses the powers the city has to implement the plan and provides evidence of how the plan will be integrated in future decision making.

New Updates

- The framework Integrates the lessons learned from leading climate action plan frameworks including: Deadline 2020, EcoAct, ICLEI, and Carbon Law (see table below) and offers a priority action table for mitigation and adaptation, specified by city types.
 - The city carbon targets update to the OPCC drew inspiration from C40 and Arup's **Deadline 2020**

Table 1: Comparison of target-setting programmes

PROGRAMME	2030 TARGET	2050 TARGET	NOTES
C40 Deadline 2020	c.2.9 tCO ₂ /capita	Zero	Scope 1 and 2 only
EcoAct / WWF France	1.1 tCO ₂ /capita	Zero	Scope 1, 2 and 3
ICLEI	2.2 tCO ₂ /capita	-	Scope 1, 2 and 3
Carbon Law	50% reduction / decade	96% reduction over 45 years	Scope 1, 2 and 3
OPCC	50% reduction between 2018 and 2030	Zero	Scope 1 and 2 only

Further to the data above, ‘Deadline 2020’ (C40 Cities and Arup, 2016) indicates that different types of cities in the C40 network have different projected average Scope 1 and 2 emissions. Based on the data presented in the report, the breakdown is as follows:

Table 2: ‘Deadline 2020’ projected emissions

TYPOLOGY	DESCRIPTION	PROJECTED AVERAGE EMISSIONS (TCO ₂ /CAPITA)		
		2018	2030	2050
Early Peak	High GHG/capita, low GDP/capita	c.5.6	c.5.4	0
Late Peak	Low GHG/capita, low GDP/capita	c.4.2	c.4.4	0
Steady Decline	Low GHG/capita, high GDP/capita	c.3.1	c.1.3	0
Steep Decline	High GHG/capita, high GDP/capita	c.6.8	c.2.3	0

- Three **fair allocation principles** that dominated the global debate were considered in the updated framework:
 - **Equality** - All people should have equal rights to emit emissions, regardless of level of development.
 - **Responsibility** - Linked to the ‘polluter pays’ principle that there is a responsibility for contributing to climate change both historically and in the future.
 - **Capacity** - the ability to solve the problem should be considered.
- The framework was heavily influenced by the IPCC Special Report 1.5 and the International Energy Agency (IEA) follow up.
 - Taking these into consideration rather than focusing on a carbon budget, OPCC focused on **requiring cities to have a mid-term and a long-term target for Scope 1 and 2 emissions** (i.e. 2030 to reduce per capita emissions in-line with a global reduction of 50% and 2050 to reduce total emissions to net zero).
 - Scenarios are taken from SR1.5 - compatible with 1.5 DTT and small overshoot (<0.1 DC). As model spread is large they do not take absolute emissions, but the ratio of per capita emissions reduction required between 2018 and 2030 which presents a much more consistent picture.
 - Leaving aside Latin America, all regions are expected to reduce per capita emissions by 40-60 % by 2030.
- Other OPCC consideration included:
 - Balancing policy pragmatism and analytical robustness.

- The calculations of the targets must be repeatable and to a certain extent automated.
- The resulting updated methodology was a 2030 target of 50% reduction against 2018 per capita emissions (Scope 1 and 2), adjusted using country HDI weighting, and a 2050 target of zero emissions (Scope 1 and 2).
 - Advantages and disadvantages can be seen in the figure below:

ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easily communicated and tested • Relative to 2018 emissions, so largest emitters have largest targets in absolute terms • Clear link to referenceable IPCC data • Larger reductions from more developed nations • Requires all cities to continue to act 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less transparent to the general public • HDI may not accurately represent city development • No consideration of hard-to-measure Scope 3 emissions

Calculation Methodology for the Target Setting Assessment

- Create or find the city's population series and annual GDP growth series from 1990-2100 using available resources (e.g. UN population change statistics, medium variant scenario, and Economics Intelligence Unite GDP growth normalization factors).
- Use the GDP growth series to modify the reported total inventory emissions and estimate the total emissions in the target start year and in 2018 and calculate the total emissions in the target end year by applying the reported target percentage reduction.
- Calculate the HDI reduction factor and calculate the science-based 2030 emissions.
- Calculate 'per capita' emissions in the target start and end year, and in 2018, 2030 and 2050.
- Test the city targets by interpolating between the 'per capita' emissions in the reported target start and end year and comparing against the science-based 2030 and 2050 emissions.

Action-Oriented Feedback

- The OPCC is designed to offer action-oriented feedback tailored to each participating city
- Climate actions in similar cities give a useful indication of typical approaches. However, more useful feedback advises the participating city on the largest opportunities for accelerated climate action.
 - A C40 and McKinsey report developed climate action pathways to achieve 90% carbon reductions by 2030 which help guide feedback for mitigation based on six city typologies (see table below), each of which differs by their potential for climate action on buildings energy, electricity generation, transit and mobility and waste.

TYPOLOGY	GDP CAPITA RANGE (\$)	POPULATION RANGE
Large Low Income Leapfrog City	0 - 4,500	NA
Low Income Megacity	4,500 - 11,000	NA
Large Semi-Dense Middle Income City	11,000 - 21,000	NA
Middle Income Megacity	21,000 - 37,000	NA
Large Dense City	>37,000	>1,000,000
Small High Income Innovator City	>37,000	<1,000,000

- To develop a process to apply these typologies to cities outside the C40 network, correlations were tested using the C40 cities data and city typology was found to be strongly correlated to GDP per capita, so that often cities could be accurately assigned to one of the six typologies using this metric alone (with the exception of 'Large Dense Cities' and 'Small High-Income Innovator Cities').
- It's important to note that the typology analysis provides cities with a 'likely' perspective on the climate opportunities and constraints and there will always be anomalies within each typology

Quantitative Pre-screening and Feedback

- The quantitative pre-screening process focuses on **carbon reduction targets, GHG inventories and climate action plans**. A list of indicators along with the scoring criteria and weights is applied (sub-categories assessed: Vision - political commitment, Targets and goals: mitigation targets, adaptation targets, Evidence for action planning - emission reporting, risk and vuln. assessment, Action plan for mitigation and adaptation)
- The framework used to score climate action in cities could be useful in developing a guideline of what is important when cities develop their own reduction targets and climate action plans.
- The pre-screening city feedback report is an automated summary of the prescreening analysis, along with the tailored city feedback based on the emissions inventory and climate hazards.
- The deep-dive city feedback report is a detailed summary of the deep-dive assessment. The scores are aggregated and presented in the 'Impact' and 'Vision' matrix, compared against all the other shortlisted cities. Key recommendations will be added based on the assessor's comments.

Consumption-Based Emissions

- Consumption-based emissions are now considered in shortlisted cities as are appropriate actions taken to reduce them.
- If they do not have a CBE inventory, the backstop is to use data published by the OECD which is published at a national scale (OECD, 2015) and compares 'production emissions' with 'final demand'. Using these ratios, the shortlisted cities production-based emissions will be adjusted.
- This is an estimate and will be updated as new city-specific research is published

WWF - One Planet City Challenge (2021)

Title: Updated Assessment Framework - Technical Document 2021

Author(s): World Wildlife Fund (WWF)

Description: The latest Updated Assessment Framework for the OPCC 2021-2022 cycle.

Relevant Changes or Additions since 2019 Framework

- Now 600 cities from 53 countries on 6 continents have taken part at least once in the OPCC

- OPCC is now connected more with other initiatives such as the Science Based Targets Network and the Race to Zero Initiative.
- Changes in the ‘Scoring Criteria’ have put more emphasis on emissions reporting and mitigation targets including a fair-share element, and slightly less emphasis on political commitments (3 criteria were added and one removed).
 - ‘Political Commitment’ criterias were consolidated and 1 criteria was removed
 - No ‘signed letter’ needed anymore
 - A ‘Mitigation Targets’ criteria was added
 - GHG targets should align with a 1.5 trajectory **based on fair-share budget**
 - Two ‘Emissions Reporting’ criteria were added
 - The size of the boundary of the emissions inventory in relation to the city boundary
 - Consumption-based emissions inventory
- Changes in the score weighting and added more points (i.e. importance) to emissions reporting and risk or vulnerability assessment, and less emphasis on political commitments.
 - Political Commitments maximum score was 10 now 5 (decrease)
 - Mitigation Target maximum score was 40 is now 39 but there are more opportunities to get points/lose points (slight decrease)
 - Emissions Reporting maximum score was 20 is now 24 (increase)
 - Climate Change Risk or Vulnerability Assessment maximum score was 20 is now 23 (increase)
 - Adaptation Actions Climate Action Planning maximum score was 25 is now 24 but there are more opportunities to get points/lose points (slight decrease)
- The Framework has added a Data Integrity Diagnosis wherein OPCC explains how it verifies the status of cities’ reported data for qualitative attributes
 - The diagnosis assesses city data in terms of quantitative rules which describe expected responses for key indicators using an **expected range of results, expected order of magnitude, or based on a calculation with reference to another response (See table below).**

Table 2. List of rules verified by OPCC Data Integrity Diagnosis.

DESCRIPTION OF INDICATOR	PROPOSED CONSTRAINTS
Current and projected population figures for years	The current population lies within the expected order of magnitude. The projected population does not exceed reasonable overestimate based on multiple of year.
City-wide emissions by sector breakdowns	Figures lie within the expected order of magnitude and do not exceed reasonable overestimate based on multiple of population. The sum of sector breakdowns matches total emissions.
Historical/base year city-wide emissions inventories	Emissions figures lie within expected order of magnitude and do not exceed reasonable overestimate based on multiples of population and inventory period dates.
City-wide base year emissions reduction targets by sector and total.	Target figures lie within the expected order of magnitude and do not exceed reasonable overestimate. Sub-sector emissions targets sum up to the total target figure.
Renewable energy or electricity target	Target figures lie within the expected order of magnitude and do not exceed reasonable overestimate based on a specified unit.
Current renewable energy installation	Figures lie within the expected order of magnitude and do not exceed reasonable overestimated based on a specified unit.
Energy efficiency targets	Target figures lie within the expected order of magnitude and do not exceed reasonable overestimated based on a specified unit.

- The Framework has added a Confidence Assessment to assess the level of evidence and level of agreement which speaks to the quality of information and reliability in the reported data
 - The table below shows the indicators used to measure confidence.

Table 4. Agreement and Evidence indicators of OPCC's Confidence Assessment.

CATEGORY	INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
Evidence	Data integrity and completeness	For 'Vision' Indicators only, this is the number of Data Integrity Diagnosis checks the city passes (see Section 4).
	Data completeness	For 'Impact' indicators only, this is an assessment of the completeness of the reported data.
	Data quantity	This relates to the amount of data provided by the city. For both 'Vision' and 'Impact' this includes the number of published (or in-progress) planning documents, as well as an assessment of the quantity of data points relating to inventories, targets and actions.
	Data age	For both, 'Vision' and 'Impact', this assesses how recent the reported data points are. More recently assessed/published/collected information results in a better score for this metric.
Agreement	1.5 °C alignment with 2030 SBT alignment	We assess if the city's self-reported target is aligned to the 2030 science-based target (SBT), which is coherent with the global 1.5 °C pathway. A score is awarded based on the correspondence between the two.
	1.5 °C alignment with net-zero target	This compares the presence of a net-zero target by (or before) 2050 against whether the city self-reported a target aligned with the global 1.5 °C pathway. A score is awarded based on the agreement between the two.
	Action planning alignment	This compares a city's reported hazards and actions to determine whether the city has reported consistent and appropriate actions and hazards.
	Mitigation action alignment	This assesses the alignment between planned emissions reduction and the reported targets.

- Adaptation actions are included in the framework that are taken from the IPCC AR5 report
 - The actions are not based on impact but on achievability
- AR5 is not used to update the target setting 1.5 C Alignment Method (still says it uses SR 1.5)

OPCC Participant Booklet (2021)

Title: One Planet City Challenge - Participant Booklet: Information for OPCC cities (2021-2022)

Author(s): World Wildlife Fund (WWF)

Description: The booklet is designed to provide local governments with general information on the One Planet City Challenge and guidance that complements the instructions found on the CDP-ICLEI Unified Reporting System.

Overview

- The booklet lays out the purpose and process of the OPCC and connects the OPCC to other initiatives that have developed since the 2019 framework was published (i.e. The Science-Based Targets Network and Race to Zero)
- Opportunities for cities to engage in programs, offered by local WWF offices, on specific topics such as food, nature-based-solutions, adaptation, plastic waste or transportation are mentioned as part of OPCC .
- To participate in the OPCC, cities report their climate actions, strategies and data on the CDPICLEI Unified Reporting System. The OPCC data requirements are aligned with the Common Reporting Framework of the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy (GCoM).
- The six stages of the challenge are clearly laid out for cities to understand the OPCC in whole (see figure below), details on how to participate and links for further details:

- **Stage 1: Registering and Reporting: Cities must**
 - Register interest via Local WWF office or via email
 - Join the OPCC through the CDP-ICLEI Unified Reporting System
 - Enter data on the Reporting System in adherence with the reporting requirements for the OPCC, which aligns with the Common Reporting Framework of the Global Covenant of Mayors (GCoM).
- **Stage 2: Assessment**
 - data submitted will be evaluated against WWF's assessment framework and its 'scoring criteria'. This focuses on carbon reduction targets, greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories and climate action plans.
- **Stage 3: Feedback on 1.5 C Alignment**
 - Each participant will receive a 'Feedback on 1.5 °C Alignment' report with our assessment of whether a city's climate targets are aligned with science-based targets, whether mitigation actions align with main emissions sectors and whether adaptation actions map effectively to climate risks.
- **Stage 4: Evaluation by the OPCC Jury**

- An international jury of urban experts, will choose national and global winners based on
 - Ambitions mid- and long-term mitigation and adaptation targets
 - Evidence-based action planning based on engagement with a broad set of stakeholders
 - Clear commitments to tackle the effects of climate change along with strong support from mayors/councils and dedicated resources
 - **Stage 5: Promotion and Global Awards**
 - national and global leaders will be recognized and rewarded through a series of award ceremonies, conferences, press releases, social media posts, videos and more.
 - The aim is to celebrate successful climate action and highlight cities that are ambitious about mitigation and resilience building.
 - **Stage 6: Public Engagement and Support**
 - Up to 3 finalists per country will be profiled in the global public engagement campaign 'We Love Cities' to inspire, raise awareness, offer the public a way to engage and celebrate, and strengthen bonds between the public and their local governments.
- The booklet helps increase the Ease of Use for the OPCC method with a simple and clear explainer of the OPCC, how to participate and links for further information.

Method 3: The Tyndall Local Carbon Budget Tool

Summary Table:

Tyndall Local Carbon Budget Tool	
City coverage	408 sub-national regions/local authorities have available carbon budget reports on the Tyndall Website ready to be used
City typologies	Cities are not categorized into typologies.
Cities pathways aligned with 1.5°C	Tyndall uses AR5 and AR6 carbon budgets for 1.5 and 1.7 degrees to determine the global carbon budget which is then downscaled
Relation to Verification Principles (Target Setting)	<p>Science-Based: The methodology is based on published papers (most recent is from 2022) Carbon budgets are determined by downscaling 1.5 C and 1.7 C global budgets from AR6 and the UK's current policy (net-zero by 2050)</p> <p>The method for downscaling the global budget to national budgets is based on a 2020 paper (Anderson et al. 2020) and creates new categorizations for developed vs developing countries.</p> <p>Equity: Tyndall considers equity both on an international scale and inter-regional/city scale For equity on an international scale, the global carbon budget is downscaled to national budgets using a method detailed in Anderson et al. 2020, where developing countries are</p>

allocated the majority of the global budget (peaking in 2025) and the remainder of the budget is distributed based on "Grandfathering" (i.e. historic emissions)

For inter-city/regional equity City carbon budgets are downscaled from the resulting national budget using a "Grandfathering" (historic emissions) approach. Population-based and GDP-based approaches showed too much variation and unrealistic decarbonization rates.

Robustness & Transparency: Tyndall is weaker in robustness compared to other methods as it is limited in the scopes and gasses it considers. Transparency on the other hand is high and well detailed in the papers they publish.

For GHGs only CO2 budgets were used because there aren't IPCC budgets for the other gasses.

For sectors the budgets are limited to energy use (power, heat, cooling, transport, and industry). Aviation, Shipping, and Military were subtracted from the national budget before downscaling. LULUCF is considered neutral globally, and a global overhead for cement is subtracted before downscaling to a national scale. CDR and offsets are not considered in the budget because of the lacking evidence, increasing vulnerability, and risk of undermining early action.

For transparency, the carbon budget reports provided to cities are publically available and based on a published report. The paper highlights assumptions, their implications, and justifications and emphasizes the importance of doing so.

Applicability & Ease of Use: The city/regional carbon budget reports are easy to acquire and understand. The reports are thorough in their explanation and provide references and explanations of key terms. The website also provides names of the report authors and an email for assistance

Practical & Context Relevant: While reports are very easy and practical to use they can only be made for countries with appropriate and fairly robust datasets. Currently this is limited to the UK, Sweden, Norway, and the Netherlands).

The method can only be used for GHGs with a global budget which is currently only CO2 but it can easily be updated when new GHG budgets are available or budgets change with temperature targets

[Tyndall Carbon Budget Tool \(March 2018\)](#)

Title: Quantifying the implications of the Paris Agreement for Greater Manchester

Author(s): Tyndall Manchester Climate Change Research

Description: The report is part of the Setting City and Area Targets and Trajectories for Emission Reduction (SCATTER) project and translates the "well below 2°C" commitment enshrined in the Paris Agreement into 1) a long-term carbon budget for Greater Manchester, 2) a sequence of five-year carbon budgets, and 3) a date of effective 'carbon neutrality' for the region.

Overview

- The SCATTER method was developed by the Tyndall center at Manchester University for the Greater Manchester Combined Authority (GMCA)
- This report expands on the SCATTER method with an analysis to downscale the UK carbon budget to Manchester.

- The carbon budgets presented in the report apply to CO₂ emissions from the energy system, excluding Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF), aviation and shipping.
- This report focuses on the 2 degree target and equity commitments set by the Paris Agreement and does not address the 1.5 degree target.
- The resulting budgets are smaller than the UK's legislated carbon budgets

Overview of the Carbon Budgeting Method

- Based on the full report, the determination of the carbon budget for a city entails 7 steps:
 1. IPCC AR5 global carbon budgets taken as the starting point
 2. deduction is made as a 'global overhead' for process emissions arising from cement production. also assume that there is no net deforestation at a global level
 3. An allocation is made to non-OECD (industrializing) nations leaving a remainder for the richer OECD members
 4. The UK is apportioned a share of the OECD budget to provide a national carbon budget range. The apportionment is made according to two regimes, i) population and ii) "grandfathering" of recent emissions (2010 to 2015).
 5. Assumptions and estimates are made about the level of future emissions from aviation, shipping and military transport for the UK. These emissions are then deducted from the national budgets as a 'national overhead' to derive final UK energy only carbon budgets.
 6. Greater Manchester is then apportioned part of the energy only UK carbon budget based on **three different regimes to give a small range of budgets**: population, grandfathering and Gross Value Added (GVA). Table 1 in the papers shows 6 different approaches to the regimes together with grandfathering on the UK level. The final recommendation is obtained by averaging.
 7. Illustrative emission pathways are developed which are in line with those budgets. Within this range of budgets a 'recommended carbon budget' for Greater Manchester is proposed as the mean of the budget range.

LULUCF Recommendations

- The report LULUCF recommendations include:
 - LULUCF achieves absolute zero CO₂ emissions, on an annual basis, by 2038 aligned with the year of carbon neutrality.
 - Post 2038 the rate of LULUCF emission reductions/sequestration continues to increase, reaching a maximum rate by around 2045. Thereafter, the sector continues to provide a stable level of annual sequestration across the century.
 - GM's emissions from LULUCF achieves net zero cumulative CO₂ emissions for the period 2018 to 2100

Emissions from Aviation

- The report states it is important that emissions from flights taken by GM citizens are monitored because if aviation emissions were to increase at a UK level then the available 2°C compatible budget for the city-region would be reduced and the city has some influence regarding the airport

- For consistency with the assumptions in this report, GM should play its part in ensuring that the emissions from UK aviation follow a static path to 2030 and then steadily decline to zero by 2075.

Sequestration and Offsetting

- Non-CO2 Emissions are handled in this report through extra sequestration through LULUCF
- The report does not recommend entering into offset relationships but sets advice if the city pursues them

Key Messages

- Manchester can make an appropriate contribution to the 2 degree C commitment in the Paris Agreement by:
 - Holding cumulative carbon dioxide emissions at under 15 million tonnes (range of 8 - 24 MtCO₂) from 2018 onwards
 - Initiating an immediate program of mitigation delivering an annual average of 13% cuts in emissions. The analysis also provides the goal of a 98% reduction of 2015 CO₂ emissions by 2050.
 - Beginning a program of reducing emissions from Land Use, Land Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF). The program consists of reaching zero LULUCF emissions by 2038 with net sequestration thereafter.
- The method has been implemented on the following two websites: <https://scattercities.com/> and <https://www.anthesisgroup.com/about/our-technology/scatter/>

Tyndall Carbon Budget Tool (July 2018)

Title: Quantifying the implications of the Paris Agreement for the city of Manchester (2018)

Author(s): Tyndall Manchester Climate Change Research

Description: This report complements the SCATTER report, by downscaling global carbon budgets to Manchester. It's an earlier iteration of the Tyndall Carbon Budget Tool Reports.

Overview

- This is a shorter complementary report of the earlier report of the same name shown above
- The report details the different carbon budgets developed using various apportioning techniques

Apportioning the UK budget to Manchester City

- The report considers 3 apportionment regimes to allocate the UK energy-only CO₂ emissions budget to Manchester: Grandfathering, Population, and Gross Value Added (GVA)
- A recommended carbon budget is then assigned made up of the mean of all the allocation regimes.
 - This budget is valid for the 2 degree commitment given that aviation and shipping emissions are reduced at the levels outlined in the SCATTER report

- The method for LULUCF emissions is also taken from the SCATTER report where the cumulative emissions from 2018 to 2038 is compensated with carbon removals from 2039 to 2100.
- Given the absence of robust non-CO2 emissions data, the report recommends the LULUCF pathway should be adapted so as to include additional sequestration in order to help compensate for any cumulative non-CO2 emissions within the Manchester boundary.
- The table below details the percentage reductions calculated for Manchester in the report:

Table 3: Percentage reduction of emissions for the CO₂-only scenarios out to 2050 in relation to 2015

	GF-Pop	Pop-Pop	GVA-Pop	GF-GF	Pop-GF	GVA-GF	Recommended pathway	LULUCF
2020	39%	34%	30%	54%	47%	42%	41%	33%
2030	83%	75%	69%	95%	91%	86%	83%	70%
2040	95%	91%	86%	99%	98%	97%	95%	105%
2050	99%	97%	94%	100%	100%	99%	98%	113%

[Tyndall Carbon Budget Tool \(2022\)](#)

Title: What does the Paris Climate Change Agreement Mean for Local Policy? Downscaling the remaining global carbon budget to sub-national areas

Author(s): Kuriakose et al./ Tyndall Manchester Climate Change Research

Description: The most recent Tyndall report where the authors used 3 different national carbon budgets for the UK and downscaled them to sub-national areas using 3 different allocations factors.

Overview

- The paper details the methodology for downscaling a Paris-aligned 1.5 and 1.7 global carbon budget to sub-national areas, focusing on emissions from energy (power, heat, cooling, surface transport and industry).
- The resulting budgets and annual emission reduction rates vary significantly, reflecting the implications of both high-level methodological choices and local factors, including economic activity, energy system structure and population.
- The methodology is broken into 6 steps outlined in the figure below:

Fig. 1. Key steps in determining sub-national carbon budgets.

- The report details the considerations, complications and implications regarding each step in the methodology
- The three **allocation approaches** used when downscaling from the national budget are **Grandfathering** (account for past emissions), **Capability-based** (based on Gross Value Added [GVA]) and **Egalitarian-based** (based on population).

Methodology Overview

- Step 1: Selection of the National Carbon Budget
 - 2 IPCC AR6 headline budgets are used as well as one from the UK's Committee on Climate Change (CCC) Balanced Net Zero (BNZ) 2050 pathway
 - The downscaling of global budgets is performed using a grandfathering approach wherein the remaining global budget is initially allocated to "developing country parties", but still leaves a viable budget for "developed" countries
- Step 2: Sub-National Allocation
 - The scope of emissions was determined using results from the SCATTER project and a workshop of twenty local government representatives with the following results
 - Aviation, shipping, and military transport were considered national overhead and are not downscaled.
 - The remaining budget was allocated to subnational scales based on egalitarian, grandfathering, and capability approaches which focused on the **ratio of the subnational to the national**.
 - The **3 national budgets** are downscaled to **12 UK sub-national regions** using the 3 allocation approaches then to the **408 UK local authorities** based on the national budget that relates to 1.7 degrees C using the three allocation approaches.

Other Relevant Notes

- Grandfathering, as an allocation method, is determined to be more "appropriate" (i.e. realistic) than capability or egalitarian allocation methods with a decarbonization range of 7-16% reduction per year (for a 1.7 degree budget).

- The 3 different national carbon budgets varied a lot. They included 2 budgets based on the IPCC carbon budgets for 1.5 (1150Mt) and 1.7 (2050Mt) and a carbon budget based on a balanced linear path to net zero carbon emissions by 2030 and 2050 (4611Mt).
- Net-zero targets with interim targets are considered bad because they are not directly connected to a temperature target and can end up having a carbon budget 4x the budget associated with the 1.5 degree limit.
- There's lots of variation in population, economic activity, and per capita income compared to average for the UK which makes capacity and egalitarian allocations vary widely and they miss lots of socio-economic factors. Grandfathering does a better job of reflecting these factors but it still lacks complexity.
- Only CO2 was used because there aren't IPCC budgets for the other gasses. This is ok for the UK but not for a more agriculturally based nation
- Sectors are also limited to energy use (power, heat, cooling, transport and industry). Aviation, Shipping and Military were subtracted from the national budget before downscaling
- LULUCF are considered neutral on a global scale and a global overhead for cement is subtracted before downscaling to a national scale.
- CDR and offsets are not considered in the budget because of the lacking evidence, increasing vulnerability, and risk of undermining early action.

Other Methods

[EcoAct - Le Défi Climatique des Villes](#)

Title: WWF - Le Défi Climatique des Villes (2018)

Author(s): WWF France

Description:

The report highlights the responsibility of French urban territories in terms of climate change, in regards to the Paris Agreement for ten metropolises and proposing visions of carbon neutrality and a "100% renewable energy" objective. It also puts forward sector-by-sector solutions that can be generalized and proposes ways to remove the technical and financial obstacles that still oppose the acceleration of the needed transition.

Overview

- This report focuses on French cities. A first emissions budget for France is calculated for the period 2016-2030 using HDI to reflect equity considerations.
- For the period 2031-2100, France's share of the global budget is equal to its share of the global budget.
- These French budgets are then shared amongst cities on an equal per capita basis (minding that France is a very centralized government with high redistribution geographically).
- The report considers waypoints for cities for 2020 (based on targets of existing targets), 2030 (based on the population) and for 2050 based on a global goal (a form of grandfathering). Options for negative emissions and compensations are also considered.

Le principe méthodologique

Snapshot - Australia

[Climate Review 2021](#)

Title: Australian Local Government - Climate Review 2021

Author(s): Ironbark and ICLEI

Description: The report is an overview of the local understanding of the scale of the response required, the ambition throughout the country, and the scope of climate action already undertaken by Australian councils and communities.

Overview

- Outlines the results of a survey in Australian communities about carbon emissions and target setting and provides suggestions.
- Table 9 includes a summary of all targets set by states and territories.
- Federal targets include reducing emissions by 26-28% from 2005 levels by 2030, renewable energy to increase to 33,000 gigawatt hours by 2030, and improving energy productivity by 40% by 2030
- 130 communities in Australia pledged to be zero carbon.
- A lack of funding and resourcing are the most significant barriers to reducing corporate (not city?) emissions, with the median budget to reduce emissions being \$200,000
- Snapshot Climate program partnered with Google for use more comprehensive mapping data to measure, plan, and reduce emissions

Target Setting

- The report states a consistent, equitable and science-based approach provides a framework for setting a community-wide emissions reduction target.
- Three questions are asked when setting targets: what is necessary, achievable and accountable?
- Targets are determined by downscaling carbon budgets that align with IPCC 1.5 degree scenarios with a 50-66% of limiting warming
- Fairness and equity should be considered by incorporating a council's community emissions profile, emissions trajectory and relative ability to reduce emissions.

Snapshot Community Climate Tool

Title: Snapshot Municipal Carbon Emissions - Calculation Methods

Author(s): Ironbark Sustainability and Beyond Zero Emissions

Description: The document outlines the methods employed for calculating emissions for municipalities as used by the Snapshot Climate emissions website.

Overview

- The tool (Snapshot Climate) is used for calculating carbon budgets for municipalities across Australia: [Link](#)
- Data for analysis considers **two primary categories: activity data** (measurement of activity that generates emissions) and **conversion factors** (converts activity data to emissions estimates)
- **Three tiers** of data are analyzed: **Tier 1** - Modeled data on a large scale that is scaled down, **Tier 2** - Local activity data with conversion factors from state/national/international references, **Tier 3** - Local activity data with conversion factors from local sources or actual local activity emissions data
- Included evaluation categories across **5 sectors:** Stationary Energy (grid-supplied electricity, gas), Transport (On road, Aviation), Waste (Landfill, wastewater), Agriculture (Livestock, crops), Land use change (Cropland to forestland, grassland to forestland, forestland to cropland)

Snapshot Webinar

Title: How Councils and Communities Around Australia Can Use Snapshot to Drive Action

Author(s): Ironbark Sustainability and Beyond Zero Emissions

Description: An open webinar held on Thursday 14th November 2019 to discuss how councils and communities around Australia can use Snapshot to drive action.

Overview

- Record of webinar question and answer about the Snapshot tool

- **Snapshot** highlights role of industrial sector and state/federal government in reducing local emissions
- Snapshot should not be used as a monitoring tool
- Profiles are developed in **line with the GHG Protocol Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Emission Inventories (GPC)**.
- Snapshot profile includes emissions from the following **5 sectors**: Stationary energy, transportation, waste (solid and water), and agriculture, forestry, and other land use (AFOLU)
- **GPC principles** in order: Relevance, completeness, consistency, transparency, and accuracy

[ICLEI - Multilevel climate action towards 1.5C \(2018\)](#)

Title: Multilevel Climate Action: The Path to 1.5 Degrees (2018)

Author(s): ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability

Description: The document makes the case for integrated data and coordination systems for tackling climate change at the local/city level.

Overview

- The ICLEI approach is based on a per capita correspondence of the global 45% reduction over 2010-2030 of the IPCC:
 - “we translate the IPCC emissions reductions figure for the 1.5-degree target—to cut global emissions to under 45 percent of the 2010 levels by 2030—into per capita emissions allowances”.
 - Doing so enables them to derive 2030 emissions objectives, and not simply a budget for a future period.
 - The equal per capita formula is also additive across scales that allows to compare the ambition of a city to a country’s share calculated the same way. In other words, the fair share of a city to the global effort is the same as its fair share of the fair share of the country it belongs to.
 - This also enables it to fit a city’s pledge within a country’s NDC, however, this approach focuses on equality and does not extend beyond 2030 and leaves aside the equity aspects of the CBDR-RC principle of the Paris Agreement.

Other Relevant Notes

- Subnational reporting shows how climate action supports broader sustainable development objectives.
- **Integrated data and two-way dialogue between subnational and national governments are needed.**
- Integrated measuring, reporting, and verification allow data to be compared across jurisdictions
- cCR has data from 1,060 local and regional governments.
- Subnational governments have committed to reductions of 7.7 gt CO₂e by 2020, 14.9 gt CO₂e by 2030, and 33.7 gt CO₂e by 2050

- Translate IPCC reductions to subnational governments by cutting 45% of 2010 levels by 2030.
- Talanoa dialogues are in-country consultations that jump start the review of NDCs
- The **integrated reporting platform** helps **different countries compare** and collaborate. The platform has one measurement, consistently accounts for all emissions, has a well understood emissions trajectory, good data, and can measure a city's contribution to national climate efforts
- This document is important in understanding the principles: **Ease of Use** and **Transparency**

[Greenhouse gas emissions budgets for Victoria \(2018\)](#)

Title: Greenhouse gas emissions budgets for Victoria

Author(s): Malte Meinshausen, Yann Robiou Du Pont and Anita Talberg

Description: This report was commissioned by the Australian state of Victoria to inform the assessment of possible emissions reduction targets.

Summary

- The report adapts the methods from [Robiou du Pont et al. 2017](#) to quantify emissions budget for each Australian state (the term “state” here assimilates states and territories) as a fraction of the Australian budgets calculated itself by the independent Climate Change Authority.
- The report quantifies four approaches to subnational burden sharing:
 1. grandfathering,
 2. capability,
 3. responsibility
 4. contraction and convergence (to 2030 and 2050).
- These budgets are then distributed over time to provide 4 emissions scenarios
- The average of 3 allocations (excluding the responsibility based one, which is the most lenient one to Victoria) is selected to review targets.
 - While grandfathering is not a fair concept of distributive justice, its unfair impact can be compensated by the other financial redistribution mechanisms of the national government.

Community-scale GHG Accounting Standards and Tools

[Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Emissions \(GPC\)](#)

Title: Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Inventories - An Accounting and Reporting Standard for Cities - Version 1.1

Author(s): World Resource Institute, C40 Cities, and ICLEI

Description: An accounting and reporting standard for cities working to give cities the standards and tools they need to measure their emissions, build more effective emissions reduction strategies, set measurable and more ambitious emission reduction goals, and to track their progress more accurately and comprehensively

Overview and Background

- Originally an outcome of two years of public consultation and testing by pilot cities, collaboration between ICLEI, C40, WRI and Cities Alliance Joint Work Program
- The document details:
 - **Reporting requirements** which include: accounting and reporting principles, setting inventory boundaries, robust and transparent account and reporting systems.
 - **Calculation guidance by emission source** which include: calculating GHG emissions both as an overview and in each sector (i.e. stationary energy, transportation, waste, industrial processing and product use, and agriculture, forestry and other land use)
 - **Tracking changes, and setting goals** which include: setting goals and tracking emissions over time, and managing inventory quality and verification

Relevant Notes

- Accounting and reporting principles (similar to SBTN principles) are **Relevance, Completeness, Consistency, Transparency, and Accuracy**.
- The protocol sticks to conventional accounting approach; this also means that it does not account for the peculiarities and specific needs of urban systems in an integrated way
- The protocol has been deemed **user-friendly** in [Mirabella and Allacker 2021](#)
- The GPC **does not require verification** but recommends that cities choose the level and type of verification that meets their needs and capacity
- The GPC likely to play an important role in the future as it is pushed by several target setting methodologies
- Both OPCC and D2020 point to GPC as a guide for setting up emissions inventories for cities
- The requirements for GPC demonstrate a baseline of data and human capacity city's need to meet in order to create a trusted emission inventory

CDP 2022 Cities Reporting Guidance (2022)

Title: 2022 Cities Reporting Guidance

Author(s): CDP and ICLEI

Description: A guidance document for disclosing to the CDP's 2022 cities questionnaire.

Overview:

- The platform guidance document contains comprehensive instructions on how to navigate the CDP dashboard and how to use and disclose via the Online Response System.
- Before 2019 CDP and ICLEI had two separate reporting platforms (ICLEI's carbonn Climate Registry (cCR) and CDP's reporting platform) which are now combined into one unified reporting platform managed by CDP.
- CDP and ICLEI use the climate data from the questionnaire to provide insights for local and regional governments, allowing them to track their progress, benchmark their efforts with their peers and drive further climate action
- Three pathways are provided with differing numbers of questions depending on how cities fill out the questionnaire or their preference. See pathways and number of questions in the table below.

Pathway	Number of Questions
1	27
2	34
3	40

- The modules for the questionnaire are **Governance, Assessment, Targets, Planning, and Actions**
- The questionnaire is connected to other frameworks for climate action including GCoM, Race to Resilience, Race to Zero, and Sustainable Development Goal 11.

Relevant Notes

- The questionnaire is one of the baseline or starting point for cities to report their emissions, targets, plans, and actions
- The responses to these questions make up the CDP databases and other associated databases
- The ability to fill out the questionnaire can be an indicator of a city's capacity in regards to target setting and/or action planning

Bilan Carbon

Title: The Bilan Carbone Clim'Foot tool

Author(s): Clim'Foot

Description: A Climate Footprint of Organizations (CFO) calculation tool, used during the Clim'Foot project. It takes a snapshot of organizations and is a means to estimate its GHG emissions at a given moment

Overview

- Clim'Foot is a European project to calculate greenhouse gas emissions produced by companies and entities funded by programme LIFE 2014-2020
- Developed by French Agence ADEME
- Uses Life Cycle Assessment Approach for all sectors
- The boundary definition is an ensemble of physical processes that are necessary for the existence of a human organization

Relevant Notes:

- The tool provides a contrast to the other city specific emissions accounting methods used by cities

Other Subnational or City Specific Resources

Summary for Urban Policy Makers (2018)

Title: Summary for policymakers: What the IPCC Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5 Means for Cities

Author(s): 18 Authors of SR1.5 and three additional climate experts

Description: The document was targeted at translating the SR 1.5 report’s key scientific findings and policy observations for officials and policymakers of the world’s cities and urban areas. It encourages urban policy makers to invest resources into city-level climate action. Specific city-level targets are recommended that adhere to contributing to minimizing temperature rise to 1.5 degrees. Mitigation/adaptation solutions are provided for cities and include transitions related to the energy system, urban & infrastructure system, industrial system, and land & ecosystem. The mitigation and adaptation solutions were assessed with six feasibility dimensions: economic, technological, institutional, socio-cultural, environmental/ ecological, and geophysical.

Overview

- Climate scientists need to be in communication with urban policymakers in order for global warming to be limited to 1.5 degrees.
- Four pathways are described that help limit warming to 1.5 degrees and include P1 (Innovations lead to lower energy demand, afforestation for CO2 removal), P2 (Sustainability, healthy consumption), P3 (Middle of the road, changing how energy and products are produced with less emphasis on reductions), and P4 (Resource and energy-intensive scenario, most reductions achieved from CDR)
- Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) includes bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and afforestation and reforestation.
- Emphasis on urban transition through green buildings with 80-90% lower emissions in 2050 than 2010, 5% annual rate of energy retrofits in developed countries, and new buildings being fossil-free and near zero energy by 2020.
- A 30% reduction in final energy use by the transport sector is needed by cities to limit 1.5 degrees rise.
- Electricity supply by renewables should breach 70-85% by 2050.
- The share of low carbon fuels (electricity, hydrogen, and biofuel) needs to be 12% in 2030 and 55% in 2050.
- Each mitigation and adaptation option was assessed with six feasibility dimensions: economic, technological, institutional, socio-cultural, environmental/ecological, and geophysical.
- Mitigation and adaptation options include transitions related to the energy system, urban & infrastructure system, industrial system, and land & ecosystem.

ISO Net Zero Guidelines (2022)

Title: Net Zero Guidelines: Accelerating the transition to net zero

Author(s): ISO

Description: The document provides guiding principles and recommendations to enable a common, global approach to achieving net zero greenhouse gas emissions through alignment of voluntary initiatives and adoption of standards, policies and national and international regulation.

Overview:

- This document builds on progress by voluntary initiatives, campaigns and governance
- The guidelines provide common terms and definitions, guidance and specific recommendations on:
 - Net zero guiding principles for all organizations;
 - Incorporating net zero into strategies and policies;
 - What net zero means at different levels and for different types of organization;
 - Setting and aligning interim and long-term targets based on equity, latest scientific knowledge, evidence, research and agreed good practice;
 - Actions to take to achieve these targets;
 - Greenhouse gas emission reductions within the value chain;
 - Nature protection and restoration;
 - Avoided emissions and other climate contributions beyond the value chain;
 - Removals;
 - Offsets;
 - Credits;
 - Claims;
 - Monitoring, measuring and use of appropriate and consistent indicators;
 - Equity, empowerment, fair share and wider impact;
 - Transparent reporting and effective communication.

ISO 14064

Title: Greenhouse gasses - Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals

Author(s): International Organization for Standardization

Description: This document specifies principles and requirements at the organization level for the quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and removals. It includes requirements for the design, development, management, reporting and verification of an organization's GHG inventory. The ISO 14064 series is GHG programme neutral. If a GHG programme is applicable, requirements of that GHG programme are additional to the requirements of the ISO 14064 series.

Integrity Matters: Net Zero Commitments by Businesses, Financial Institutions, Cities and Regions

Title: Integrity Matters: Net Zero Commitments by Businesses, Financial Institutions, Cities and Regions

Author(s): United Nations' High-Level Expert Group on the Net Zero Emissions Commitments of Non-State Entities

Description: Report from the UN High-Level Expert Group which sets out ten practical recommendations to bring integrity, transparency and accountability to net zero by establishing clear standards and criteria of non-state entities.

Relevant Notes:

- Put together by 17 experts appointed by the UN Secretary General

- The recommendations build on credible existing initiatives including Race to Zero and the Science Based Targets initiative and are largely focused on corporations, financial institutions and cities but regions and smaller non-state actors play an important role as well.
- **10 Recommendations:**
 1. Announcing a Net Zero Pledge
 - A net zero pledge should be made publicly by the leadership of the non-state actor and represent a fair share of the needed global climate mitigation effort.
 - The pledge should contain interim targets (including targets for 2025, 2030 and 2035) and plans to reach net zero in line with IPCC or IEA net zero greenhouse gas emissions modeled pathways that limit warming to 1.5°C with no or limited overshoot, and with global emissions declining by at least 50% by 2030, reaching net zero by 2050 or sooner. net zero must be sustained thereafter.
 2. Setting Net Zero Targets
 - Non-state actors must have short-, medium- and long-term absolute emissions reduction targets and, where appropriate, relative emissions reduction targets across their value chain that are at least consistent with the latest IPCC net zero greenhouse gas emissions modeled pathways that limit warming to 1.5°C with no or limited overshoot, and where global emissions decline at least 50% below 2020 levels by 2030, reaching net zero by 2050 or sooner.
 3. Using Voluntary Credits
 - Non-state actors must prioritize urgent and deep reduction of emissions.
 - High integrity carbon credits in voluntary markets should be used for beyond value chain mitigation but cannot be counted toward a non-state actor's interim emissions reductions required by its net zero pathway.
 - As best-practice guidelines develop, non-state actors meeting their interim targets on their net zero pathway are strongly encouraged to balance out the rest of their annual unabated emissions by purchasing high-integrity carbon credits.
 - A high-quality carbon credit should, at a minimum, fit the criteria of additionality (i.e. the mitigation activity would not have happened without the incentive created by the carbon credit revenues) and permanence.
 4. Creating a Transition Plan
 - Transition plans must:
 - Disclose short-, medium- and long-term absolute emission reduction targets, and, if relevant, relative emission reduction targets. Targets must account for all greenhouse gas emissions and include separate targets for material non-CO2 greenhouse gas emissions.
 - Detail the third-party verification approach and audited accuracy.
 - Reference credible sector pathways consistent with limiting warming to 1.5°C with no or limited overshoot (e.g. IPCC, IEA, Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS), One Earth Climate Model (OECM)) and explain any

material difference between the non-state actor's transition plan and sector pathways.

5. Phasing out Fossil Fuels and Scaling Up Renewable Energy

- All net zero pledges should include specific targets aimed at ending the use of and/or support for fossil fuels in line with IPCC and IEA net zero greenhouse gas emissions modeled pathways that limit warming to 1.5°C with no or limited overshoot

6. Aligning Lobbying and Advocacy

- As part of their transition plan and annual disclosures, non-state actors should outline the specific policies and regulations, including carbon pricing, that they would need to cut emissions in line with a 1.5°C scenario. This disclosure should specify the emissions reductions possible if the listed policies and regulation by authorities and jurisdictions were in place.

7. People and Nature in the Just Transition

- Financial institutions should have a policy of not investing or financing businesses linked to deforestation and should eliminate agricultural commodity-driven deforestation from their investment and credit portfolios by 2025, as part of their net zero plans.

8. Increasing Transparency and Accountability

- Non-state actors must annually disclose their greenhouse gas data, net zero targets and the plans for, and progress towards, meeting those targets, and other relevant information against their baseline along with comparable data to enable effective tracking of progress toward their net zero targets.
- Non-state actors must report in a standardized, open format and via public platforms that feed into the UNFCCC Global Climate Action Portal to address data gaps, inconsistencies and inaccessibility that slow climate action.
- Non-state actors must have their reported emissions reductions verified by independent third parties. Special attention will be needed to build sufficient capacity in developing countries to verify emission reductions.

9. Invest in Just Transitions

- There needs to be a new deal for development that includes financial institutions and multinational corporations working with governments, Multilateral Development Banks and Development Finance Institutions to consistently take more risk and set targets to greatly scale investments in the clean energy transition in developing countries.

10. Accelerating the Road to Regulation

- In order to ensure rigor, consistency and competitiveness, regulators should develop regulation and standards in areas including net zero pledges, transition plans and disclosure, starting with high-impact corporate emitters, including private and state-owned enterprises and financial institutions.
- The challenge of fragmented regulatory regimes should be tackled by launching a new Task Force on net zero Regulation that convenes a community of international regulators and experts to work together towards net zero.

ICLEI Notation Key

Title: The Value of Using Notation Keys in City Scale Greenhouse Gas Emission Inventories: Learning From Absent Data

Author(s): ICLEI

Description: A document on best practice on reporting to inform about missing or poor data. It assessed 127 inventories and demonstrated where and how to use notation keys for city scale GHG emission inventories.

Comparing city-level target setting methods

SBTN 2020

Title: Results of the assessment of GHG emission reduction target setting methodologies for cities (2020)

Author(s): Science Based Targets Network

Description: This document introduces different existing reduction target setting methodologies. It serves as the starting point for cities looking to set science-based targets

Relevant Notes

- **Multi-criteria assessment of five GHG emissions reduction target setting methodologies:** D2020, EcoAct, One Planet City Challenge, Tyndall Centre, and C-Fact
- Science Based Targets Initiative (SBTi): adoption of science-based targets in the corporate sector. A group of organizations have formed the SBTN to help companies and cities set science-based targets for climate, water, biodiversity, land, and ocean systems.
- The key principles for assessing SBT: **Science-driven, Equitable, Completeness, Usability**
- Variables for Science-driven principle: Temp target, likelihood, carbon budget, overshoot, scenario used, target consistent with budget, treatment of transferable units
- Variables for Equitable principle: Emissions allocation approach, equity perspectives, country equity considerations, consideration of city profiles
- Variables for Completeness Principle: GHGs considered, Emissions scopes, differentiation of sectors, target type, consideration of growth, excluded emissions, and carbon sinks
- Variables for usability principles: Documentation and resources, data needs, usability, open source, updatability
- All methodologies have **carbon budgets that align with the Paris agreement**, except for the older C-FACT methodology
- All consider equity, but in different ways. Similar themes involve anchoring key targets at fixed dates with a mechanism that accounts for equity, the deadline of net zero by 2050 (except C-FACT), correcting for equity using some indicator of development, and using an approach to divide the global budget to city level

- All methodologies mention that further development work is needed to **improve inventory processes, data accuracy, and collection of non-CO2 gasses**. At the same time, **precise measurements should not be mandatory to take action** on climate change
- **"Net-zero" must be defined** and what is required to achieve it.
- **Cities Issue Hub** should play a main role in: monitoring and evaluation the application of methodologies to a city context, monitoring and evaluating the progress made towards target achievements, and researching and socializing the main lessons and best practices on how to achieve ambition GHG mitigation targets for cities
- **Output:** Guide for cities (last Nov., 7 languages), embedded in the raise to zero initiative, campaign from UN, Missing: validate cities targets - in the way of the method; High level check: reporting system against 3 methods. Results there. Quality? How to reach targets? Roll out. 5000 USD for validation

Table: Starting point to derive validation approach

<p>Note on origin of project as a general orientation (see also the accompanying technical paper):</p> <p>In the past, SBTN performed some target validation, but efforts have been</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • limited in scope (number and type of cities), • boundaries (city-wide, not sectoral), and • recurrence (based upon project timelines as compared to city needs). <p>SBTN's Cities Hub demands independent and <u>continuously available technical capacity</u> to verify emission reduction targets and assess compatibility with 1.5°C.</p> <p>Questions to be addressed by validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If all the data submitted is correct, does this target represent a <u>fair share</u> of emission reduction, <u>in line</u> with 1.5° C? [PHASE 1]; and, 2. Are the data and assumptions behind the target setting valid enough to deliver robust targets? [PHASE 2]. <p>Methods assessed: D2020, EcoAct, OPCC, SCATTER, C-FACT</p>	<p>Consequences for our project:</p> <p>Structure our suggestions covering what was missing (choice and naming of validation criteria, selection of tests to be carried out, selection of type of cities to be tested).</p> <p>Reminder: we test but do not target improving methods!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>do it differently:</i> e.g., alternative typology • <i>go deeper:</i> include sectoral, include consumption-based accounting • <i>towards self-testing:</i> test user friendliness of how to run validation <p><i>Realism:</i> Focus on 1.5, but this needs to be verified with the consortium because recent developments may make 2.0 more useful instead or in addition.</p> <p>Validation of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Method:</i> Correctness and fairness of target set (by comparing with alternatives) 2. <i>Input:</i> Testing robustness of target (by testing data and assumptions behind target) 3. <i>Output:</i> ex-post testing of derived action (with the help of real data and experiences gathered from 5-years-implementation, e.g., 2020 targets)
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<p>Results from prior assessment</p> <p>Principle 1 – Methodology should be updated relative to latest climate science. Table summarizes temperature targets, likelihood, carbon budget, overshoot, reference scenarios, target years, target consistency. Discussion concludes that methods fail to acknowledge recent discussions (e.g. carbon budgets, negative emissions and CDR). At least to better document.</p> <p>Principle 2 – Allocation approach, equity & differentiation considerations. The method is only summarized. Discussion: Equity is almost always discussed from the perspective of regional/country equity and its impact on development, little on production-based or consumption-based accounting, inter-generational equity is not discussed at all.</p>	<p>Consequences for our project:</p> <p>Not all use a carbon budget approach, not all document reference scenarios, consistency with budget only for D2020 and Scatter determined. Is it relevant to assess C-FACT at all? Have tests been carried out? Were the methods verified? Here we can develop a checkbox list that shows more transparently what has been accounted for (e.g., the report mentions intergenerational aspects,</p>
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Principle 3 – Completeness (scopes/source differentiation, GHGs, exclusions, removals and use of carbon credits). Table summarizes GHG and scopes addressed, target type, emissions excluded, growth assumptions, CO2 removals and carbon credits - if any. Discussion: All methodologies address Scope 1 and 2 emissions and only one methodology attempts to address Scope 3 emissions. Not all methodologies have a consistent inventory programme. Most methodologies do not take into consideration different cities' typologies. GHG are different in all methods. Little documentation on exclusions of certain emission sources. Recommendation to set supplementary targets for non-CO2 gasses exists.

Principle 4 – User friendliness. Table reports on method documentation and open source (for method and tools), resources, data needs, usability (e.g., additional user input), updatability. Room for improving documentation, the main barrier appears to be a lack of good quality city inventories.

Overall conclusions: all to improve inventory processes, data accuracy and collection of non-CO2 gasses as well as sources such as international aviation, but “precise accounting” should not be a precondition for decisive commitments and action.

Test reported in technical attachment:

Emission targets 2030*	Absolute emissions (tCO ₂ e) 2030		Energy related absolute emissions (tCO ₂)	Emissions per capita (tCO ₂ e)		Energy related emissions per capita (tCO ₂)
	City	OPCC*		D2020	Tyndall	
Greater Amman	6,046,910	10,017,739.9	2,441,149.58	1.45	2.40	0.58
Pasig	907,939	1,707,345	497,896.7	0.98	1.85	0.54
Seoul Metropolitan Government	17,729,294	20,266,227.0	194,147.2	1.77	2.03	0.02
Stockholm	907,615	1,236,290	35,154.9	0.89	1.21	0.03
Rio Grande	489,333	1,398,302.5	291,339.1	5.04	14.39	3.0
eThekwini Municipality	13,375,066	29,640,166*	3,396,811.6	2.99	6.62	0.76
Heidelberg	344,973	349,966.3	7,245.6	2.33	2.37	0.05
City of Calgary	7,542,637	6,263,287.8	30,230.8	5.37	4.46	0.02
City of Hobart	191,064.54	168,083.9	11,240.8	3.22	2.83	0.19

Table 6: City 2030 absolute emission targets

development stage, within country equity, and city profiles).

Have tests been carried out? E.g., confronting alternatives? Were the methods verified? Check verification by developing a questionnaire to interview method experts.

Have tools been tested? Who has assessed these criteria? Are there rules for updating/ verification/documentation/communication? Interview experts. This hints towards weighing.

This is the actual test carried out.

SBTN City guide 2020

Title: Science-Based Climate Targets: A Guide for Cities (2020)

Author(s): Science Based Targets Network

Description: This document provides step-by-step directions for cities on how to set climate targets.

- Document was created to guide cities in choosing a methodology for setting a science-based target by 2030 and a net zero target by 2050
- Science-based refers to aligning with Earth's limits and societal sustainability goals. Targets must be measurable, actionable, and time-bound objectives.

- The following principles for targets must be considered: they must be science-driven, equitable, and complete
- Carbon budgets will vary based on responsibility (historical and late emissions), capacity (dependent on socio-economic development), and intergenerational justice (duties towards future generations)
- Table included in the report provides a broad estimate science-based targets based on a city's GDP and current emissions per capita
- The report provides three methodology options and the steps to calculate targets based on these options.
- Deadline 2020 Methodology: Data points required include GDP per capita, GHG emissions inventory / baseline (2015), and Baseline population and population growth until 2050. Outcome includes emissions trajectory for your city type indicating 2030 and 2050 targets.
- One Planet City Challenge (OPCC): Data points required include HDI score and city-wide emissions baseline as close to 2018 as possible. Outcome includes reduction targets for per capita 2030 and 2050 emissions, based on 2018 levels.
- Tyndall Centre: Data points required include CO2 emissions from energy from cities in the UK. If not in the UK, more data is required, such as national CO2 emissions from aviation, shipping, and military. Outcome includes the city-level carbon budget for CO2 energy emissions, trajectory of CO2 energy emissions until 2100, and a year in which CO2 energy emissions would reach zero or near zero.
- Cities can join the UNFCCC's Race to Zero by pledging to reach net zero by mid-century, planning how to reach net zero and interim target, proceeding to take action by updating climate action plan with targets, and publishing progress annually.

Table: [Guide provided to cities](#)

- Read the Science Based Target Network's [guide](#) to science-based climate targets
- Watch our recorded and upcoming [webinars](#)
- Read our [guidance](#) on cities disclosure
- Check our [FAQs](#)

Fig. Summary across some method reviews

Choice	C40 D2020	ICLEI	WWF - OPCC	WWF - Ecoact	Victoria
1.	Global	Global	Global	Global	Global
2.	Budget + bottom-up	Dynamic	Dynamic	Budget	Budget
4.	CDC + Capability + Equality	Equality	Capability (HDI)	Capability (HDI) + Equality	Equality/CDC - Capability - Responsibility
5.	Non-additive	Additive	Non-additive? (HDI)	Non-additive?	Additive

	C40 D2020	ICLEI	WWF - OPCC	WWF - Ecoact	Tyndall - Manchester	Victoria
Allocation	Budget	Pathway	Pathway	Budget	Budget	Budget
Equity approach	Capability Equality	Equality	Capability	Capability Equality	Equality, Grandfathering Capability	Equality Capability Responsibility Grandfathering
Applicable to all?	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes

Webinars and Presentations

Here we review webinars and presentations related to target setting to complement information gained from the literature review. Many of the webinars presented below came from presentations that took place at COP 27.

[Enabling Universal Participation in the Enhanced Transparency Framework \(ETF\)](#)

Title: Enabling Universal Participation in the Enhanced Transparency Framework (ETF)

Speakers: Xuehong Wang (Manager-UNFCCC Transparency Div); Carlos Fuller (Ambassador-Permanent Repr. of Belize to the UN); Jacob Werksman (European Commission-EU Lead Negotiator); Thelma Krug (Vice-chair-IPCC); Racquel Moses (Race to Zero Global Ambassador); Amir Sokolowski (CDP Global Director-Climate Change)

Description: A panel discussion at COP 27 part of the “Together for Transparency” series focused on discussing the new “Enhanced Transparency Framework”

Relevant Notes:

- **Defining characteristics of transparency:** Colorless (i.e. devoid of perspective), Comprehensive, Accessible, Coherent, Consistent across time
- **Benefits of ETF:** Accountability (local and nationally), Capacity building, Opportunities to partner, Demonstrates what's happening and can create momentum, Helps with public education.
- **Challenges:** Can divert resources from action, Need for capacity (this is a big one, developing countries can rely on coalitions with other countries, need help retaining talent, and collaborating) both people and finances, avoiding fragmentation
- The ETF will help with accountability which needs to start at home and be focused on those who have the capacity first
- CDP is focusing on showing people where they are on the journey to net-zero (and where they need to be) rather than simply saying they're doing good or bad
- New emission monitoring technology may help with real time verification (e.g. combining satellite and on the ground monitoring). Normally self-reporting can take 2 years (serious lag in data) which new technologies can help speed up.
- Peer-reviews should be done by peers in capacity to the reviews are fair

Net-Zero: Science-based not Science-Fiction

Title: Net-Zero: Science-based not Science-Fiction

Speakers: Alberto Carrillo Pineda (Chief Technical Officer - SBTi); Emma Watson (Head of Standards - SBTi); Kaya Axelsson (Net Zero Policy Engagement Fellow - Oxford University); Paulina Ponce de León Baridó (Managing Director and Partner - Boston Consulting Group); and Scarlett Benson (Beyond Value Chain Mitigation Lead - SBTi)

Description: Webinar for a COP 27 presentation on the SBTi net-zero standard, focused primarily on setting science-based net-zero targets for the private sector.

Relevant Notes:

- Standards are important as they drive voluntary ambitions for decarbonizations by mobilizing ambition actors (change from 1 of 5 to 1 of 3 companies in the forbes 100 creating ambitions in one year)
- SBTi standard was launched in 2021. In one year 100 companies have gone through the target-setting process and 1500 are in the process. All voluntarily.
- **SBTi Net-Zero Standards:** 1) Short-term targets (5-10yrs), 2) Long-term Targets (1.5 aligned, 2015), 3) Neutralizing residual emissions (using CDR), 4) Beyond value chain mitigation (finance and nature conservation)
- **Steps:** 1) set base year, 2) calculate emissions, 3) set boundary, 4) Set target year, 5) Calculate target
- **Prioritization in order:** 1) Abatement, 2) Beyond value chain mitigation, 3) neutralization

- Panelist Discussion
- ISO guidelines
 - just published which are a reference guide for leaders regarding net zero
 - created by a collaboration of 1200 participants
 - For organizations, cities, and governments
 - Meant to be comprehensive, pointing decision makers to the available resources and standards like SBTi
 - Not a certified standard, only a comprehensive guide
- There's a need for convergence because the inconsistency of standards slows the action
- Beyond Value Chain Mitigation is companies going above and beyond net zero by investing in climate mitigation and potentially adaptation through finance (e.g. carbon credits or removal)
 - The aim is to drive climate finance to places its most urgently needed (e.g. ecosystems close to tipping points, CDR tech)
- Incentives for action include unlocking finance designated for climate change, securing supply early as demand increases, developing knowledge, and getting a competitive advantage.
- Regulation is still far from where we need to be. CDP voluntary disclosure started 22 years ago but it's moving now: by 2025 50% of global pop and GDP will be covered by mandatory emissions disclosure
- SBTi Focus: target setting, guidance, validating targets, publishing valid targets on the website. The next step is tracking progress.

[Enhanced Transparency Framework: What it is and why it matters for Least Developed Countries](#)

Title: Enhanced Transparency Framework: What it is and why it matters for Least Developed Countries

Speakers: Fernanda Alcobé (Climate Change Researcher - IIED); Milan Dhungana (Under-Secretary Technician - Ministry of Forests and Environment, Nepal); Yamikani Idriss (Environmental Officer - Ministry of Natural Resources and Climate Change, Malawi)

Description: An online webinar streamed during COP 27 which gives a short overview of the Enhanced Transparency Framework (ETF) focusing on what it means for least developed countries (LDCs).

Relevant Notes:

- What's Included:
 - Actions - Mitigation and Adaptation
 - Support - Financial and Technical (Needed, received, and provided)
- What's been enhanced
 - More comprehensive regarding support and actions, how plans are being implemented
 - Reported on a 2-year schedule

- Advice for LDCs: use guidelines, identify stakeholders who have the needed data, communicate the benefits of reporting to stakeholders, build capacity with coalitions and universities

City-level data

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